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MASTER THESIS:

Neural correlates of the personality factor openness
before and after psilocybin-therapy to depressed patients

Student: Manca Peskar

ID number Maastricht University: i6157356

Programme: Research Master Cognitive Neuroscience

Cohort: 2017-2019

ID number Imperial College London: 01659210

1st Supervisor: David Erritzøe, MD, PhD

2nd Supervisor: Kim Kuypers, PhD

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Abstract

Converging evidence implies that psilocybin-assisted intervention holds promise for the treatment of depression, and that it promotes enduring increases in the openness trait of personality in healthy and depressed individuals. Additionally, depression indicators and openness display a negative association, and low openness is considered a risk factor for treatment-resistant depression. The present study investigated the relationship between openness and its neural correlates in treatment-resistant depression preceding and following a psilocybin-assisted intervention, to (i) extend the findings of personality neuroscience from healthy to depressed population and (ii) unfold the neural mechanisms that could be mediating clinical improvements. *A priori* seeds were selected in anterior cingulate (ACC) and precuneus (PCU), and an fMRI resting-state functional connectivity (RSFC) analyses were applied to the whole brain on a voxel-wise level. Preceding the intervention, caudal and dorsal ACC, and posterior PCU displayed openness-related RSFC with medial and lateral prefrontal cortices, as well as motor areas and thalamus; areas previously implicated in cognitive flexibility, working memory, and motor and attentive control. Following the intervention, perigenual ACC and posterior PCU expressed openness-related RSFC confined to pre/postcentral gyri and frontal pole; areas implicated in sensorimotor integration, emotional states recognition and flexible retrospective/prospective cognition. The data imply that higher levels of openness might be facilitating these cognitive processes and task performance via stronger communication among the regions denoted above. The findings hold important implications for depression, which is often characterised by cognitive impairments.

1 INTRODUCTION

The present thesis resides on the intersection between three fields – psychedelics, personality and depression. The introduction, therefore, consists of three major sections, each one presenting relevant concepts and findings from the literature on (i) the psychedelic drugs, focusing primarily on psilocybin, (ii) the personality structure, with a special emphasis on openness domain and its neural correlates as detected by functional magnetic resonance imaging, and (iii) depression, or more specifically, treatment-resistant depression. Despite being seemingly separated, connections between the fields and their overlap are dutifully addressed and elaborated on whenever possible. The last, fourth, section of the introduction provides a summary of the most relevant findings, leading up to the purpose, research questions and hypotheses of the present study.

1.1 Psychedelics

1.1.1 Introduction and mechanisms of action

Psychedelic drugs or ‘psychedelics’ are pharmacological agents capable of producing profound changes in one’s ordinary conscious experience, characterised by distortions in one’s sense of self and time, perception of reality, feelings, mood states, thoughts and behaviour (Hofmann, 1968). In 1957, an English psychiatrist Humphry Osmond (1957) coined the term *psychedelic* in an attempt to adequately describe and reflect the nature of experience these drugs produced. The term originates from Greek language and combines the words *psyche* (mind, soul, spirit) and *dēlos* (clear, manifest). It literally translates to *mind manifesting*, implying the drugs’ beneficial properties to human psyche.

Psilocybin is a naturally occurring psychedelic compound contained in over two hundred mushroom species of multiple genera, including the genus *Psilocybe* (Nichols, Johnson, & Nichols, 2017). These mushrooms are commonly known as the ‘magic mushrooms’. Once ingested, psilocybin undergoes rapid dephosphorylation, producing an active metabolite *psilocin*. In other words, psilocybin is a prodrug of psilocin, whose chemical structure closely resembles the one of the neurotransmitter serotonin (5-hydroxytryptamine; 5-HT). Molecular similarity allows psilocin to mimic the effects of serotonin in the central nervous system (Hasler, Bourquin, Brenneisen, Bär, & Vollenweider, 1997). Psilocybin, lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD), dimethyltryptamine (DMT), and mescaline, constitute a class of *classic hallucinogens* or *serotonergic psychedelics*, as they primarily, but not exclusively, act on 5-HT

system (Nichols, 2004). Their unique and profound effects on human consciousness, however, depend on agonistic (or partial agonistic) activity to a specific 5-HT receptor subtype, called 5-HT_{2A}. A recent PET study showed a positive relationship between the intensity of subjective effects of psilocybin and the levels of 5-HT_{2A} receptor occupancy (Madsen et al., 2019). Moreover, the blockade of 5-HT_{2A} receptors caused by antagonistic action of ketanserin, was shown to attenuate subjective psychedelic effects of psilocybin (Vollenweider, Vollenweider-Scherpenhuyzen, Bäbler, Vogel, & Hell, 1998) and LSD (Kraehenmann et al., 2017). In addition, the majority of 5-HT_{2A} receptors were found located in the cortex, as opposed to the subcortical structures, with high-level association/integration cortices such as posterior cingulate cortex (PCC) expressing particularly high density of the respective receptor type, and primary motor cortex expressing the lowest density (Forutan et al., 2002). Taken together, these observations could explain why the acute effects of a serotonergic psychedelic might primarily affect the cognition and perception, while the effects on the motor system appear relatively negligible (Carhart-Harris et al., 2014).

1.1.2 Acute and long-term effects

The psychological effects of an acute psychedelic state are most commonly assessed by the *Altered State of Consciousness* (ASC) questionnaire which quantifies a subjective state of consciousness across the following eleven dimensions (Studerus, Gamma, & Vollenweider, 2010): experience of unity, spiritual experience, blissful state, insightfulness, disembodiment, impaired control and cognition, anxiety, complex imagery, elementary imagery, audio-visual synaesthesia, and changed meaning of percepts. Although acute effects of psilocybin or LSD can be somewhat reminiscent of the symptomatology of psychosis (Hofmann, 1980), and elicit transient strong or extreme fear in humans (Griffiths, Richards, McCann, & Jesse, 2006), they have been, paradoxically, shown to promote enduring positive changes on human psyche that outlive the acute effects. A within-subject study in healthy participants showed elevated levels of optimism 2 weeks after the administration of LSD as opposed to placebo (Carhart-Harris et al., 2016). Additionally, LSD has been shown to positively affect mood, attitudes about one's self and their own life, promote positive social effects and desirable behavioural changes in healthy volunteers, enduring 12 months after the psychedelic experience (Schmid & Liechti, 2018). Moreover, a double-blind study showed increased levels of well-being and life satisfaction, persisting up to 14 months after a single high dose of psilocybin in 64% of psychedelic naïve healthy individuals (Griffiths, Richards, Johnson, McCann, & Jesse, 2008). Lastly, a recent report from an online survey study (Griffiths, Hurwitz, Davis, Johnson, & Jesse,

2019) in 3476 participants, retrospectively assessing the effects of a single experience with a serotonergic psychedelic, elucidated and confirmed psychedelic's lasting positive impact on purpose in life and life satisfaction.

1.1.3 Psychedelic-assisted therapy

In early 1950s, several psychotherapeutic practitioners recognised the potential psychedelics hold as psychotherapeutic aids. The pioneering work from Busch & Johnson (1950) showed that psychedelics represent powerful tools facilitating self-reflection of one's own past. Psychoanalytic practitioners used psychedelics in their psychotherapeutic sessions with the intention to decrease clients' psychological defence mechanisms, which allowed internal personal conflicts to arise to the surface of manifestation where they could be worked through with a therapist (Cohen, 1970). Clinical conditions that are characterised by some form of mental suffering, such as malfunctioning, involuntary, repetitive, or rigid thought processes (and behaviours), were, therefore, thought to potentially benefit from psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy. Over the last two decades, a number of clinical pilot studies on the effects of psychedelics and especially psilocybin, have shown promise for the treatment of resistant depression (Carhart-Harris, Bolstridge, et al., 2016), end-of-life anxiety in terminally ill patients (Griffiths, Johnson, & Carducci, 2016), alcohol and tobacco addiction (Johnson, Garcia-Romeu, Cosimano, & Griffiths, 2014; Krebs & Johansen, 2012), and obsessive-compulsive disorder (Moreno, Weigand, Taitano, & Delgado, 2006).

In contrast to the conventional psychiatric treatment model that typically consist of several months-to-years long daily administration of a pharmaceutical drug (Sackeim, 2001), the major advantage of the psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy is that positive effects are usually achieved after a single administration (for a review, see Johnson & Griffiths, 2017). While the exact efficacy rates of this alternative treatment approach are currently a focus of research, and clear guidelines for the administration protocols have not yet been established, the centres adopting psychedelics into their research, tend to follow a common direction with a particular focus on the *set* and *setting* (Johnson, 2008; Preller & Vollenweider, 2018). Setting pertains to the physical arrangements of the environment in which a psychedelic is taken, and encourages a choice of a safe and familiar environment, pleasant room temperature, general comfort, as well as pleasing olfactory stimuli and music. Set, on the other hand, refers to a state of mind of an individual prior to taking psychedelics. It encompasses one's expectations, personality

characteristics, and mood, among the others, and is discussed in detail with the psychedelic session facilitators.

General progression of a developing psychedelic-assisted treatment model for psychiatric disorders introduces the administration of psilocybin as a part of structured support therapy (Carhart-Harris, Bolstridge, et al., 2016; Johnson & Griffiths, 2017). Over the course of several days, participants undergo (i) a screening session to assure the study-specific inclusion criteria are met, e.g. the absence of history of psychosis, (ii) a preparation meeting, in which participants get familiarised with the upcoming session's course, (iii) typically, a single psychedelic session (or two), during which continuous monitoring and interpersonal support is provided, while the participants focus on introspection, (iv) and an integration session, in which the content experienced during the session is addressed and discussed in order to provide the basis for enduring desirable changes. This structured attention to the set and setting of the psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy has been found to minimise the risk for adverse effects and increase the positive effects (Johnson & Griffiths, 2017). Apart from moderately increased blood pressure (Griffiths et al., 2011) and the occurrence of post-session transient headaches (Johnson, Sewell, & Griffiths, 2012), studies report a favourable safety profile of psilocybin with low risk of harm.

Alongside of sustained positive changes to human psyche discussed above, this one-off-sessions of psychedelic-assisted support therapy have also been shown to promote increases in personality factor openness in healthy (Maclean, Johnson, & Griffiths, 2011) as well as depressed patient (Erritzøe et al., 2018) populations. Because a personality profile of an individual has repeatedly been shown to remain relatively stable in the adulthood, with the slightest changes observed only after decade-long periods (Back, Schmukle, & Egloff, 2009; Furr, 2009), the increases in openness induced by a single psychedelic session seem rather remarkable. The field of personality thus offers an insightful study example for investigating how those deep psychological changes are facilitated within the framework of psychedelic-assisted support therapy. The topic is further elaborated on in the following sections.

1.2 Personality

1.2.1 Factors of personality

Personality refers to a characteristic set of behavioural, cognitive and emotional patterns of an individual. The Personality Inventory NEO PI-R developed by Costa & McCrae (1992) is one of the most frequently used tools for assessing a personality profile. It delivers information

about the *Big Five* personality factors or domains, known as neuroticism, extraversion, openness, conscientiousness, and agreeableness.

Neuroticism is associated with an inclination to experience emotions of negative valence, such as irritability and anxiety (Costa & McCrae, 1992), and is thought to reflect an individual's sensitivity to threat and punishment (Clark & Watson, 2008). Conversely, *extraversion* represents a factor associated with a tendency to experience positive emotions, such as sociability and talkativeness (Costa & McCrae, 1992), and has been tightly linked to the sensitivity to reward (Clark & Watson, 2008). *Conscientiousness* represents an individual's ability to inhibit impulses in order to respect rules or follow goals that do not deliver immediate results, and has been associated with occupational success, self-discipline, and orderliness among the others (Ozer & Benet-Martinez, 2006). *Agreeableness* reflects acknowledging other people's needs, rights, and wishes, and is as such related to altruism. Cooperation, compassion, politeness, and aggression represent some of the traits clearly associated with the agreeableness domain of personality (Graziano, Habashi, Sheese, & Tobin, 2007). *Openness*, which is of particular interest to the present study, relates to the ability of flexible processing of abstract and perceptual information and has been linked to creativity, imagination, and intellectual engagement (DeYoung, Peterson, & Higgins, 2005). NEO PI-R inventory assesses an individual's position along the openness dimension across the following six facets: openness to fantasy, openness to aesthetics, openness to feelings, openness to actions, openness to ideas, and openness to values (Costa & McCrae, 1992).

As already mentioned, the positions along the Big Five personality dimensions are believed to remain rather stable throughout the adulthood (Back et al., 2009; Furr, 2009). Relative stability of personality factors on one hand and reliable differences observed between individuals on the other, have inspired the investigations of neurobiological basis subserving personality with the hypothesis that the behavioural differences should somehow also be reflected and modulated by differential recruitment of neural substrates.

1.2.2 Personality neuroscience

The attempts to identify neural correlates of personality factors using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) can be coarsely clustered into structural and functional MRI (fMRI) investigations. Structural MRI techniques, such as voxel-based morphometry (Good et al., 2001) and surface-based morphometry (Hutton, Draganski, Ashburner, & Weiskopf, 2009) tend to yield a rather inconclusive or even contradictory results regarding the neural basis of

personality (Coutinho, Sampaio, Ferreira, Soares, & Gonçalves, 2013; DeYoung et al., 2010), and are thus regarded as sub-optimal for this field. Similarly, diffusion MRI studies investigating white-matter integrity associated with personality domains suffer from the lack of reproducibility, and as such do not offer unambiguously convincing insights (Bjørnebekk et al., 2013; Xu & Potenza, 2012).

The majority of the available evidence in personality neuroscience comes from fMRI studies, which can be further categorized based on the employed paradigm into task-based or resting-state (for a review, see Kennis, Rademaker, & Geuze, 2013). Task-based studies rely on the assumption that differences in information processing while performing a certain task may be rooted in the differences in personality (Yarkoni, 2015). Therefore, it is the cognitive mechanisms presumably associated with personality traits that are being studied, rather than the personality traits *per se* (Canli et al., 2001). Additionally, task-based fMRI personality studies raise the concern about the choice of the task itself, specifically in terms of construct validity for a particular personality trait (Dubois, Galdi, Han, Paul, & Adolphs, 2018).

In an attempt to overcome task-based constraints, the present project adopted the fMRI resting-state functional connectivity (RSFC) approach. Resting-state data are obtained in a task-free condition without imposing any specific cognitive demands on a participant. The data are further approached by functional connectivity analysis, which assesses the degree of co-activation between distinct brain regions by correlating their respective blood oxygen level dependent (BOLD) fMRI time series (Lowe, Dzemidzic, Lurito, Mathews, & Phillips, 2000). A common hypothesis-based approach, which was also utilised in the present project, selects a set of predetermined seed regions and compares each seed's mean time series to the time series of a whole brain on a voxel-wise level. RSFC provides a measure of communication and information flow between regions on a network scale. Because complex cognitive processes that make up a personality arguably rely on a dynamic interplay between anatomically separated regions, RSFC analysis offers an important large-scale perspective to understanding neural mechanisms supporting cognition (Greicius, Krasnow, Reiss, & Menon, 2003; van den Heuvel & Hulshoff Pol, 2010). Typically, the analysis is performed on slow (0.1 Hz) spontaneous fluctuations in the BOLD signal (Cordes et al., 2001).

Adelstein and colleagues (2011) provided the first and to our knowledge the only examination of the intrinsic functional organization of the brain and its association with the Big Five personality factors. The choice of anterior cingulate cortex (ACC) and precuneus (PCU; including PCC) as seed regions in RSFC analysis was motivated by the areas' known involvement in higher-order executive control and supporting information integration, respectively (Kelly et al., 2009; Margulies et al., 2009). *Figure 1* depicts positions of individual seeds along with their associated function (further addressed in discussion).

Figure 1. The seeds. Locations, labels and associated functions of selected seeds. sgACC = subgenual ACC; pgACC = perigenual ACC; supgACC = supragenual ACC; dACC = dorsal ACC; cACC = caudal ACC; aPCU = anterior PCU; cPCU = central PCU; pPCU = posterior PCU; PCC = posterior cingulate cortex. Adapted from Adelstein et al., 2011.

Openness to experience was found to predict RSFC in an area comprising a fair portion of medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC) including ACC, as well as area within PCC – the two areas correspond to the core hubs of the default mode network (DMN) and have been linked to self-related thoughts (Andrews-Hanna, Reidler, Sepulcre, Poulin, & Buckner, 2010). Openness was also found to be

Figure 2. Big five personality factors predicted functional connectivity. Colour coding refers to individual personality factors. Significant findings are collapsed across all the seed regions and the valence of factor-RSFC relationship. White depicts brain regions whose RSFC could be predicted by multiple personality factors. LH = left hemisphere, RH = right hemisphere. Adapted from Adelstein et al., 2011.

predictive of RSFC within dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (dlPFC) – a region whose activation is strongly associated with working memory (Balconi, 2013) and creativity (Jung et al., 2010); and portions of superior and middle temporal gyri – which play a crucial role in hearing, speech and language (Howard et al., 2000). *Figure 2* provides an overview of brain regions whose RSFC with the seeds showed significant relationship with openness (in orange), while a detailed and comprehensive contribution of each individual seed's RSFC is presented in *Table 1*.

Table 1

Individual seed's RSFC with other brain regions expressing relationship with openness.

Seed	Functionally connected regions (NEG)	Functionally connected regions (POS)
sgACC	R Precuneus R Middle Temporal G. L Inferior & Middle Frontal G. L Rectal G.	R Medial Frontal G. L Precentral G.
pgACC	R Frontal Pole BI Inferior Frontal G.	L Superior Frontal G. R Medial Frontal G. R Cingulate G. L Subcallosal G.
supgACC		BI Cingulate G.
dACC	L Precentral G. R Postcentral G. L Precuneus	
cACC	R Medial Frontal G. L Superior Frontal G.	L Superior, Middle & Inferior Frontal G. R Medial Frontal G. L Superior Temporal G. BI Middle Temporal G. R Inferior Temporal G. R Temporal Pole L Inferior Occipital G. L Occipital Pole L Rectal G. R Anterior Cingulate L Cuneus
aPCU		L Lingual G.
cPCU		R Pyramis
pPCU	BI Postcentral G. R Precentral G. R Medial Frontal G. L Transverse Temporal G.	

Note. NEG / POS = negative / positive relationship with openness; L = left; R = right; BI = bilateral; G. = gyrus
Regions were identified based on local maxima. Adapted from Adelstein et. al., 2011, Supporting Information.

Adelstein and colleagues (2011) show unique, mostly non-overlapping, patterns in brain's effective connectivity associated with individual personality domains¹. This finding argues in favour of resting-state fMRI being suitable for investigating complex constructs such as personality.

As briefly mentioned, the results outlined above are indicative of an association between openness and the core regions comprising the DMN (Adelstein et al., 2011). Beaty and colleagues (2016) tested this prediction using structural equation modelling and applying graph theory methods to resting-state fMRI data in healthy participants, and showed that the functional architecture of DMN, e.g. its efficiency of information processing, could reliably be predicted by the level of openness. In other words, the higher the openness, the more effective DMN's functioning. Beaty and colleagues suggested the observed link might be due to the imaginative or creative note that characterizes both openness and DMN; higher levels of creativity are predominantly observed with people high in openness (Beaty & Silvia, 2013), and the generation of creative ideas has been linked to DMN (Andrews-Hanna, Smallwood, & Spreng, 2014). DMN has also been associated with the thoughts of self in relation to others, self in time, and mind wandering (Andrews-Hanna et al., 2010). Taken together, these results suggest that 'a more efficiently functioning DMN may allow people high in openness to more effectively engage the neurocognitive processes associated with this network' (Beaty et al., 2016, p. 778).

1.3 Depression

Depression is a mental disorder characterised by mood disturbances and accompanied by psychosomatic symptoms, anhedonia, as well as suicidal tendencies (Ebmeier, Donaghey, & Steele, 2006). Patients suffering from depression are often caught in a cycle of rigid thought pattern shaped by a pessimistic view and self-criticality, and are usually unable to break out of this state of auto-aggressive introspection (Carhart-Harris et al., 2014). In other words, their self-reflective thought processes and mind wandering are subjected to negative cognitive bias (Beck, 1967). According to the World Health Organization, depression is the leading cause of worldwide disability, affecting over 350 million people (Greenberg, Fournier, Sisitsky, Pike, &

¹ The study investigated RSFC in relation to all five personality traits; however, only the result on openness are presented in the main text, as these are the focus of the present project. For completeness, results on the remaining four factors are summarised below: *neuroticism* was shown to predict RSFC with dorsomedial prefrontal cortex and middle temporal gyrus; *extraversion* could predict RSFC in lateral paralimbic cortex and fusiform gyrus; *agreeableness* was shown to predict RSFC in extrastriate and sensorimotor regions; *conscientiousness* could predict RSFC in portions of ACC, PCC and medial temporal lobe.

Kessler, 2015; Smith, 2014). Despite several types of available antidepressant medications, such as monoamine oxidase inhibitors (MAOIs), tricyclic antidepressants (TCA), serotonin-selective reuptake inhibitors (SSRI), serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRI), and atypical antidepressants (X. Li, Frye, & Shelton, 2012), up to 60% of patients fail to show significant symptom improvements following their first adequate course of antidepressant therapy (Sackeim, 2001). The nuisance associated with treatment management is often due to the drugs' delayed onset of the therapeutic effects, the occurrence of side effects, and general unresponsiveness or intolerance to the drugs (Pacher & Kecskemeti, 2004; Rush et al., 2006; Sackeim, 2001). Even when remission is initially achieved, approximately 50% of patients relapse over the course of one year (Rush et al., 2006).

1.3.1 Antidepressant effects of 5-HT_{2A} agonism

The developing paradigm for treating depression using serotonergic psychedelics offers a new course of action, namely direct stimulation of excitatory 5-HT_{2A} receptors or 5-HT_{2A} receptor agonism (Hasler et al., 1997), through which antidepressant effects might be exerted on a biochemical level. Komater and colleagues (2012) showed that the blockage of 5-HT_{2A} receptors using the antagonist ketanserin, blocks the psilocybin-related mood improvements in healthy participants, suggesting that 5-HT_{2A} receptors have an important role in mood regulation. Several neurobiological mechanisms have been implicated with 5-HT_{2A} signalling that could mediate antidepressant effects of psychedelics. Firstly, in depression, functional hyper-connectivity within DMN (Lemogne, Delaveau, Freton, Guionnet, & Fossati, 2012) and a strong positive relationship between DMN's functional connectivity and the levels of depressive rumination have been observed (Berman et al., 2011), while psilocybin has been shown to decrease the functional connectivity within DMN in healthy participants post administration (Carhart-Harris et al., 2012). Secondly, acute administration of psilocybin to healthy participants has been shown to attenuate amygdala's reactivity in response to threat-related visual stimuli, resulting in shifting the emotional biases from negative to positive (Kraehenmann et al., 2015, 2016). Thirdly, in mice, 5-HT_{2A} receptor agonism is involved in modulation of glutamatergic neurotransmission (Moreno, Holloway, Albizu, Sealfon, & González-Maeso, 2011), which is associated with increased neuroplasticity and neurogenesis (Vollenweider & Komater, 2010), both of which have been found deficient in depression (Duman, 2004). Lastly, in mice, acute psychedelic-assisted 5-HT_{2A} receptor stimulation could promote normalization of inflammatory cytokines levels (Nau, Yu, Martin, & Nichols, 2013), which have been detected in high amounts in depression (Réus et al., 2015).

The two distinct levels across which psychedelics exert their effects, e.g. neurobiologically by the mechanisms described above, and behaviourally by sustaining positive effects on well-being after a single dose (Ross et al., 2016), appoint to why psychedelics might hold a unique and favourable position as a potential alternative treatment option for depression. In 19 treatment-resistant depressed patients, who had been at the time of study enrolment struggling with depression for 17.7 years on average, Carhart-Harris and colleagues (2018) showed a significant reduction in depressive symptoms persisting up to six months after psilocybin-assisted support therapy. The greatest effect size was observed five weeks after the treatment with nine participants meeting treatment response criteria. Similarly, in life-threatening disease, reductions in anxiety and depression have been observed persisting at least six months following psilocybin administration (Griffiths et al., 2016; Grob et al., 2011; Ross et al., 2016).

1.3.2 Depression, psychedelics & personality change

Across two studies, 58% (Griffiths et al., 2008) and 78% (Griffiths et al., 2019) of healthy participants rated their experience with a psychedelic as being among the five most personally meaningful experiences of their lives. With that in mind, it is not surprising that a psychedelic experience could drive a change in a person's characteristics that otherwise seem relatively resistant to change, as in the case of personality (Terracciano, McCrae, Brant, & Costa, 2005). Despite the relative stability of a personality profile, specific occasions do appear to influence it, namely, significant life events such as divorce (Costa, Herbst, McCrae, & Siegel, 2000), remarriage (Mroczek & Spiro, 2003), and career success (Costa et al., 2000), or long-lasting treatment interventions such as antidepressant medication therapy (Costa, Bagby, Herbst, & McCrae, 2005). The former example reveals an associative rather than causal relationship between personality change and a specific life event, partly due to the challenges of creating personality-changing events under experimental conditions, while the latter resides in the outcome of long-term treatment management of clinical populations. The only occasion, to our knowledge, offering the opportunity to investigate personality changes in response to discrete and experimentally manipulated event included the administration of a psychedelic. In healthy participants, MacLean, Johnson, and Griffiths (2011) demonstrated increased levels of openness 1–2 months after a high-dose psilocybin session as compared to their baseline measures. Notably, in participants who have had a complete mystical experience, the elevated levels of openness persisted for over a year.

Moreover, Erritzøe et al. (2018) investigated the changes in personality profile following psilocybin-assisted intervention session in treatment-resistant depressed patients. A three-month follow-up showed increases in openness and extraversion, as well as decreases in neuroticism compared to the baseline measures. Interestingly, treatments with commonly prescribed antidepressants, such as SSRIs, were found to promote the changes along neuroticism and extraversion dimensions in the same direction as did psilocybin-based intervention (Roberts et al., 2017); however, the change in openness seemed to be uniquely driven by the psychedelic characteristic of the treatment. Personal communication with David Erritzøe, MD, PhD (data not published), revealed that the data collected via online *Psychedelic Survey* platform support the observations denoted above – increases in openness following a psychedelic session were observed in both healthy and depressed participants, while the changes in neuroticism and extraversion pertained solely to depressed patients in which the shift towards the normative scores was observed. Changes in openness, therefore, seem to reflect inherent property of the psychedelic experience and are thought to occur independently of the presence/absence of a mood disorder.

Cognitive flexibility and creativity represent the core features of openness and are predominantly observed in individuals who express high levels of openness (Costa & McCrae, 1992). Conversely, rigid and repetitive thought patterns, or in other words cognitive inflexibility and convergent thinking, represent nearly a benchmark of depression (Beck, 1967), and could be seen as the other extreme of the same dimension, e.g. low openness. Indeed, Khoo and Simms (2018) demonstrated a negative relationship between openness and multiple depression indicators, both on a domain openness level as well as individual openness facets levels. The results for several facets remained significant even after controlling for sex, age, neuroticism and extraversion, while the openness domain could no longer explain any portion of unique variance in depression. Moreover, comparing healthy controls, individuals with remitted depression, and treatment-resistant depression, Takahashi and colleagues (2013) showed that low openness plays a unique role in predicting treatment-resistant depression, and should be considered a risk factor.

Because (i) openness and depression indicators exhibit significant negative relationship (Khoo & Simms, 2018; Takahashi et al., 2013), and (ii) psilocybin can alleviate depression (Carhart-harris et al., 2018; Ross et al., 2016) as well as promote the increase in openness (Erritzøe et al., 2018; MacLean et al., 2011), further studies investigating neural correlates of the changes

in openness following psilocybin treatment would not only enrich the literature on personality neuroscience, but also elucidate the mechanisms underlying depression.

1.4 Synopsis and the purpose of the present study

The above research demonstrates that:

- Psychedelics are potent 5-HT_{2A} receptor agonists with long-lasting positive effects on well-being, life-satisfaction, and mood.
- A psychedelic experience can lead to increases in personality factor openness, in both healthy and depressed participants.
- Personality factors, including openness, are associated with distinct and unique RSFC patterns between brain regions in healthy participants; openness, specifically, has been found to predict RSFC between the seed regions (ACC, PCU) *and* mPFC and PCC, which represent the two core hubs of DMN.
- Openness and depression indicators exhibit negative relationship, and low openness can predict treatment-resistant depression.
- Depression is affecting 350 million people worldwide and conventional therapies do not deliver significant symptom improvements in 60% of patients following their first course of antidepressant treatment.
- A single session of psilocybin-assisted support therapy appears a promising alternative treatment for depression, via stimulation of 5-HT_{2A} receptors on neurobiological level and the capability of eliciting profoundly meaningful experience on behavioural/phenomenological level.

The purpose of the present study was to assess the relationship between openness and functional connectivity in treatment-resistant depressed patients before and after psilocybin-assisted intervention. (1) Neural correlates of personality in terms of BOLD fMRI RSFC have only been demonstrated in healthy individuals (Adelstein et al., 2011). Therefore, the first research question the present study aimed to answer was how is openness associated with functional connectivity in depressed patients at baseline (e.g. before the psilocybin session). The findings on openness predicting functional connectivity between ACC/PCU seeds and mPFC/PCC regions (Adelstein et al., 2011) motivated the hypothesis that the same neural correlates could subserve the expression of personality characteristics independently of the presence/absence of depression. (2) Following psilocybin treatment, the RSFC of ACC/PCU seeds related to openness was again examined. The second research question, however, aimed to explore RSFC

in subsets of patients that responded to psilocybin intervention and the ones that did not. Because openness exhibits negative relationship with depression indicators (Khoo & Simms, 2018), the alleviation of depressive symptoms in responders and persisting symptomatology in non-responders were hypothesised to exhibit distinction in their openness-RSFC relationship. Assuming openness is more likely to be higher in responders than non-responders, it is meaningful and clinically relevant to examine if and how the nature of openness-RSFC relationship differs between the two groups.

2 METHODS

Data utilised for the present project had been obtained as a part of an open-label feasibility study, conducted by Carhart-harris and colleagues (2018). As such, the present project does not provide a comprehensive description of the protocol and materials used, but rather reports on the parts that are essential to the present project only. Previous findings in this dataset can also be found in the following publications: Carhart-Harris, Bolstridge, et al. (2016), Carhart-Harris et al., (2017), & Erritzøe et al. (2018).

The study received a favourable opinion from the National Research Ethics Service London – West London, was sponsored and approved by Imperial College London’s Joint Research and Compliance Office (JRCO), was adopted by the National Institute for Health Research (NIHR) Clinical Trials Network (CTN), and was approved by The National Institute for Health/Wellcome Trust Imperial Clinical Research Facility and Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA). Participants provided written informed consent.

2.1 Participants

Nineteen participants with diagnoses of treatment-resistant depression of at least moderate severity (scoring ≥ 17 points on 21-item Hamilton Depression Rating Scale – HAM-D; Hamilton, 1967) were enrolled in the study. Treatment-resistant depression is a form of unipolar major depression whose symptomatology could not be relieved by any of at least two preceding adequate treatments with antidepressant medications, lasting over a minimum of 6 weeks (Souery et al., 1999). Exclusion criteria were the presence or history of a diagnosed psychotic disorder, either in participants themselves or their immediate family members, history of a suicide attempt resulting in hospitalization, history of mania, presence of needle/blood phobia, positive pregnancy test, drug/alcohol dependence, and significant medical condition. Three participants were excluded from the analysis due to excessive movement while inside the MRI scanner and an additional one due to an injury in parietal cortex, leaving the final sample size of 15 participants (4 women). Their age ranged from 27 to 62 years ($M = 42.8$, $SD = 10.5$). According to their ethnic origin, 11 identified as white, 3 as black, and 1 as Hispanic. One participant completed secondary education, 7 held undergraduate degree, and 7 held postgraduate degree. On average, the participants have been unsuccessfully treated with 4.6 antidepressant medications ($SD = 2.9$) prior to the beginning of the study. Three participants had previously tried a psychedelic drug (LSD) in recreational contexts, while the others were

psychedelic naïve. All but one had undergone at least one form of psychological counselling and/or psychotherapy in their past.

2.2 Procedure

Initially, participants were scheduled a telephone interview, used to ensure that inclusion/exclusion criteria were met. Next, participants were invited to a screening visit at Imperial Clinical Research Facility (ICRF). Candidates gave written informed consent and underwent an exhaustive mental and physical health evaluation, including blood tests, electrocardiogram, urine test (for drug abuse and pregnancy), and breathalyzer. Several baseline (pre-session) behavioural measures were acquired, including personality inventory NEO PI-R (Costa & McCrae, 1992) and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI; Beck, Ward, Mendelson, Mock, & Erbaugh, 1961). Participants also met the two clinical psychiatrist who would follow and support them throughout the study. Suitable participants were then invited for a preparation visit. It consisted of a 60-minute baseline (pre-session) MRI scanning protocol, and a psychological preparation, which included (i) a discussion about psilocybin effects, (ii) a simulation of a psilocybin dosing day, and (iii) inviting participants to talk freely about their personal history and share their thoughts on the origins of depression.

Each participant then underwent two psilocybin dosing treatments which took place one week apart. On the first session a low safety dose (10mg; for assessing adverse effects) and on the second session a high therapeutic dose (25mg) of psilocybin was orally administered. All post-session results relate to the time after the second, high psilocybin dose. During each psilocybin session participants were invited to lay down with their eyes closed, listen to music and experience introspection, while the two allocated psychiatrists offered a non-directive support. One day after each dosing day participants returned for an integration session and a 60-minute post-session MRI scanning. Additional integration session took place a week after the high psilocybin dose treatment, when a post-session depression inventory (BDI) was applied. Second assessment of personality (NEO PI-R) was scheduled three months after the high-dose treatment.

2.3 Materials

NEO PI-R delivers information about one's position along the Big Five personality domains; however, this thesis reports on openness only. Each domain is assessed across six facets, and each facet contains eight items, resulting in 48 items per domain. Participants respond to items using a 5-point Likert-scale, ranging from strongly disagree (0 points) to strongly agree (4

points). The raw scores per domain range from 0 to 192 points; higher score translates to a more pronounced trait. NEO PI-R raw scores were standardised as T-scores ($M = 50$, $SD = 10$; Costa & McCrae, 1992; Costa & McCrae, 2008); however, for investigating their relationship with RSFC the present paper utilised raw instead of T-scores.

BDI is a self-rating tool delivering information about the severity of depressive symptomatology. Original version consists of 21 questions inquiring about how a participant has been feeling over the last week, ranging from *I do not feel sad at all* (0 points) to *I am so sad or unhappy that I can't stand it* (3 points). The total score ranges from 0 to 63 points; higher score indicating greater depressive severity (Beck et al., 1961).

2.4 fMRI data acquisition

Imaging was performed at Imanova Imaging Centre at Imperial College London, UK. MRI data were obtained from 3 T Siemens Tim Trio scanner together with a 12-channel head coil. Anatomical images were acquired using MPRAGE parameters: 1 mm isotropic voxels, TR = 2300 ms, TE = 2.98 ms, 160 sagittal slices, 256×256 in-plane FOV, flip angle = 9 degrees, bandwidth = 240 Hz/pixel, GRAPPA acceleration = 2. BOLD resting state fMRI data were obtained using T2*-weighted echo-planar images (EPI), using 3 mm isotropic voxels, TR = 2000 ms, TE = 31 ms, 36 axial slices, 192 mm in-plane FOV, flip angle = 80 degrees, bandwidth = 2298 Hz/pixel, GRAPPA acceleration = 2, number of volumes = 240, duration = 8 min. This imaging protocol was nested within a 60-minute-scan during which additional measures were acquired. However, those are not the focus of the present project, and are thus not reported here.

2.5 Data analysis

2.5.1 Behavioural data analysis

Personality assessment compared baseline (pre-session) and three-months follow-up (post-session) openness scores obtained with NEO PI-R. Data were analysed with IBM SPSS software using a two-tailed paired-samples *t*-test. Results are reported as $M \pm SD$.

With the reference to pre-session BDI scores, one-week post-session BDI scores were used to split participants to two subgroups according to treatment response criteria (Frank et al., 1991): *responders* ($\geq 50\%$ reduction in BDI score from pre-session to one-week-post-session) or *non-responders* (the rest).

2.5.2 fMRI pre-processing

fMRI data were analysed using the following software packages: FMRIB Software Library (FSL; Smith et al., 2004), AFNI (Cox, 1996), Freesurfer (Dale, Fischl, & Sereno, 1999), and Advanced Normalization Tools (ANTs; Avants, Tustison, & Song, 2009). The degree of in-scanner movement was assessed using frame-wise displacement (FD); participants with more than 20% of scrubbed volumes with a scrubbing threshold of $FD = 0.5$ were excluded from the analysis. The pipeline for pre-processing steps of neuroimaging data was as follows: removal of the first three volumes, de-spiking (3dDespike, AFNI), slice-time correction (3dTshift, AFNI), motion correction (3dvolreg, AFNI), brain extraction (BET, FSL), rigid body registration to anatomical scans (BBR, FSL), non-linear registration to 2 mm MNI brain (Symmetric Normalization – SyN, ANTs), scrubbing (FD threshold = 0.5) and replacing the scrubbed volumes with the mean of the surrounding volumes, spatial smoothing of 6mm - FWHM (3dBlurInMask, AFNI), band-pass filtering (between 0.01 – 0.08 Hz; 3dFourier, AFNI) and regressing out 9 nuisance regressors – 6 of them were motion-related (3 translations, 3 rotations) and 3 were anatomical, relating to the ventricles (Freesurfer), draining veins (FSL’s CFS minus Freesurfer’s Ventricles), and local white matter (FSL’s WM minus Freesurfer’s subcortical grey matter structures).

2.5.3 Seed-based connectivity analysis

According to Adelstein and colleagues (2011), 8 out of 9 selected seed regions’ functional connectivity expressed significant relationship with openness. In the present analyses, however, all 9 were selected, including the non-significant PCC. This decision was motivated by the findings showing that PCC represents a core hub of DMN (Andrews-Hanna et al., 2010), which has in turn been associated with openness (Beaty et al., 2016). After examining the data, aPCU seed had to be excluded from these analyses, because fMRI data for this region have not been acquired in all participants; this led to a final number of 8 seed regions. The bilateral seed regions were constructed as 5-mm spheres centred on the standard 1 mm MNI152 anatomical brain coordinates, and later translated to 2 mm MNI152 space. The seeds within anterior cingulate cortex included (Kelly et al., 2009): subgenual ACC – *sgACC* (MNI coordinates; \pm sign for right/left hemisphere: $x = \pm 5, y = 25, z = -10$); perigenual ACC – *pgACC* ($x = \pm 5, y = 47, z = 11$); rostral section of supragenual ACC – *supgACC* ($x = \pm 5, y = 34, z = 28$); dorsal ACC – *dACC* ($x = \pm 5, y = 14, z = 42$); and caudal ACC – *cACC* ($x = \pm 5, y = -10, z = 47$). The seeds within precuneus included (Margulies et al., 2009): central PCU – *cPCU* ($x = \pm 2,$

$y = -64, z = 45$); posterior PCU – $pPCU$ ($x = \pm 1, y = -78, z = 43$) and posterior cingulate cortex – PCC ($x = \pm 2, y = -36, z = 35$).

Mean time-series of each seed were obtained by averaging the time-series of all voxels in the respective seed region per subject per condition (pre-session, post-session). For each participant, each seed's time-series correlations with the whole-brain on a voxel-wise level were determined. The analyses were performed in FSL using general linear model (GLM). Participants' individual correlation maps were transformed to z-value maps, using Fisher's r-to-z transformation.

The relationship between openness and RSFC with *a priori* selected seeds was assessed using two separate regression analyses, separately for pre-session and post-session time points. For pre-session and post-session, group-level mixed-effects analyses were performed using FSL's FEAT (pre-whitening FILM was applied), with raw demeaned pre-session and post-session openness scores, respectively, as a regressor in GLM (FLAME 1+2). Cluster threshold was corrected to $z > 2.3$, and alpha level was kept at $p < 0.05$ (Slotnick, 2017).

Brain mask was designed to confine the analyses to the grey cortical and subcortical matter. Brain regions exhibiting significant RSFC with the seeds were identified based on the local maxima of thresholded clusters using probabilistic Harvard-Oxford cortical and subcortical structural atlases in FSL (Desikan et al., 2006; Frazier et al., 2005). Reported are the regions whose probability was equal to or exceeded 15%. Although multiple local maxima might have been detected within a single region, each region is only reported once per cluster.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Behavioural assessment

At post-session higher levels of openness were detected as compared to pre-session. A paired-samples *t*-test revealed a significant difference between pre-session raw openness score (114 ± 21.3) and post-session raw openness score (122 ± 18.1); $t(14) = -2.18$, $p = .046$.

BDI scores were used to split the participants' post-session data into two subgroups. Using the criteria for treatment response, 8 participants were classified as responders, and 7 as non-responders.

3.2 Openness-RSFC association

Several *a priori* selected seed regions and their functional connections were shown to have a significant relationship with openness scores at pre-session and post-session.

Pre-session regression analysis detected regions whose pre-session RSFC with selected seeds were associated with pre-session openness scores. dACC, cACC, and pPCU seeds were shown to express functional connectivity associated with openness; *Figure 3* depicts their overall functional connections, separated by colours according to the valence of the relationship they

Figure 3. Pre-session functional connections of selected seeds expressing significant association with openness. The position of five axial slices on the left is denoted by five blue lines across a mid-sagittal slice on the right; the numbers on top correspond to the z-coordinate of MNI152 standard space; left/right hemispheres are presented on the left/right hand sides. (Top) For illustration purposes, significant findings are collapsed across seeds (dACC, cACC, and pPCU). Hot (red-to-yellow) and cold (blue-to-turquoise) colours depict voxels expressing positive and negative relationship with openness, respectively, while the hue represents z-statistic score (see colour bar). (Bottom) Same data collapsed across the relationship valence (positive/negative), providing information on individual seed's functional connections that express association with openness. Separated by colour are each seed's functionally connected regions: sgACC – cyan; pgACC – yellow; supgACC – violet; dACC – red; cACC – green; PPC – white; cPCU – black; pPCU – blue (see location and colour code of each seed in bottom right).

exhibit with openness (positive/negative; top) or according to individual seed's functional connectivity contribution (bottom). Functional connections of dACC and cACC expressed negative relationship with openness and were confined to bilateral medial prefrontal cortex, including portions of anterior cingulate and paracingulate gyri, as well as frontal pole. Positive relationships with openness were observed predominantly in the right hemisphere, with the cACC seed displaying connectivity with the frontal portions, and the pPCU seed displaying connectivity with precentral gyrus and subcortical structures such as thalamus. A detailed report on the number and sizes of activated clusters, as well as the identified locations of local maxima within each cluster is presented in *Table 2*.

Table 2.

Pre-session: Individual seeds RSFC with other brain regions expressing significant relationship with openness.

Seed	Relationship with Openness	Cluster Index (number of voxels)	RSFC: Locations of Local Maxima
dACC	NEG	1 (516)	BI Frontal Pole L Paracingulate G. R Anterior Cingulate G.
cACC	NEG	1 (325)	L Subcallosal C. L Paracingulate G. L Anterior Cingulate G.
		2 (53)	R Subcallosal G.
	POS	1 (581)	R Frontal Pole BI Superior Frontal G.
pPCU	POS	1 (259)	R Middle Frontal G. R Precentral G.
		2 (154)	R Thalamus * White matter

Note. NEG = negative; POS = positive; L = left; R = right, BI = bilateral; G. = gyrus; C. = cortex; * = local maxima found within the white matter, the result is excluded from interpretation

Post-session regression analysis detected regions where post-session RSFC with selected seeds showed significant relationship with post-session openness scores. Out of eight investigated seed regions, only pgACC and pPCU exhibited RSFC that was associated with openness, both of which displayed a relationship of positive valence. Regions functionally connected with pgACC clustered predominantly on left hemisphere's postcentral gyrus and central opercular cortex, while pPCU displayed connectivity with bilateral frontal pole. *Figure 4* depicts the two seeds' overall connections separated by colour per relationship valence (top) and individual seed's connectivity (bottom), while *Table 3* provides a thorough description of the number and sizes of activated clusters as well as the locations of local maxima associated with each seed's functionally connected regions that are related to openness.

Figure 4. Post-session functional connections of selected seeds expressing significant association with openness. (Top) For illustration purposes, significant findings are collapsed across both seed regions, pgACC and pPCU, displaying regions that are positively associated with openness. (Bottom) Same data providing information on individual seed's functional connections that express positive relationship with openness. For general figure description and colour codes, please refer to Figure 3.

Table 3.

Post-session: Individual seed's RSFC with other brain regions expressing significant relationship with openness

Seed	Relationship with Openness	Cluster Index (number of voxels)	RSFC: Locations of Local Maxima
pgACC	POS	1 (398)	L Precentral G. L Postcentral G. L Central Opercular C.
pPCU	POS	1 (286)	R Superior Frontal G. BI Frontal Pole

Note. NEG = negative; POS = positive; L = left; R = right, BI = bilateral; G. = gyrus; C. = cortex

Next, participants were split according to BDI treatment response criteria to two subgroups – responders and non-responders, and the nature of their openness-RSFC relationship at post-session was examined. For the whole sample as well as the two subgroups separately, Figure 5 describes the relationship between openness and RSFC of each seed using Pearson's r correlation coefficient. Testing for significance of the difference between two correlation coefficients (in responders vs non-responders subgroups) was performed in online calculator (<http://vassarstats.net/rdiff.html>), as IBM SPSS Software does not conduct this analysis. However, because the subgroups are not entirely independent and the insufficient number of observations in each subgroup weakens statistical power (Bujang & Baharum, 2016), this analysis should be considered exploratory in nature. RSFC of pgACC exhibited a correlation with openness scores of $r(8) = .91$ in responders, and $r(7) = .71$ in non-responders. The

subgroups' openness-pgACC RSFC correlations did not differ; $p = .342$. RSFC of pPCU exhibited a correlation with openness score of $r(8) = .70$ in responders, and $r(7) = 0.88$ in non-responders. Openness-pPCU RSFC correlations of the two subgroups did not differ; $p = .447$.

Figure 5. Openness-RSFC relationship in full sample, responders and non-responders for post-session data. Each graph shows a correlation between openness and RSFC for (left) the full sample, (middle) responders, and (right) non-responders, separately for (top) pgACC, and (bottom) pPCU seeds. Pearson's r is denoted in top right corner of each graph. X-axes represent raw post-session openness scores; Y-axes represent each seed's post-session RSFC z-scores, obtained by Fisher's r -to- z transformation. Each dot represents a participant.

4 DISCUSSION

The present study was designed to explore the relationship between the personality factor openness and its neural correlates using RSFC analysis in patients suffering from treatment-resistant depression. The openness-RSFC relationship was assessed at two time points, namely preceding (pre-session) and following (post-session) psilocybin-assisted treatment intervention.

4.1 Pre-session data

Pre-session negative associations were observed between openness and RSFC of dACC and cACC seeds (*Figure 3* and *Table 2*). The two regions are commonly referred to as middle cingulate cortex (MCC; Palomero-Gallagher, Vogt, Schleicher, Mayberg, & Zilles, 2009) and are involved in higher order cognitive processes (Beckmann, Johansen-Berg, & Rushworth, 2009; Etkin, Egner, & Kalisch, 2011; Shackman et al., 2011); the dACC is primarily active during emotional conflict-monitoring, error-detection and approach-avoidance decisions, while a more posterior part, cACC, is involved in response- or action- selection and movement-execution. Openness-related functional connections of both dACC and cACC were detected within portions of mPFC (including sgACC), an affective brain area modulated in emotion-related learning, computation of expected value and reward, and monitoring of the outcomes of an ongoing action (Grabenhorst & Rolls, 2011; Koechlin, Danek, Burnod, & Grafman, 2002). The data demonstrate that stronger functional connectivity between the seeds involved in cognitive and motor control, and the regions implicated in affective aspect of actions, is associated with lower levels of openness, and vice versa. As already mentioned, mPFC is a core node of DMN, whose activity has been implicated in self-referential processing (Andrews-Hanna et al., 2010). Compared to healthy controls, depressed patients express higher DMN RSCF with sgACC (Berman et al., 2011; Greicius et al., 2007), which was in addition found to be positively correlated with the duration of the current depressive episode (Greicius et al., 2007) and rumination scores as measured by the Rumination Response Scale (RRS; Berman et al., 2011). Further analysis revealed that the observed positive correlation was indeed driven by the negative forms of rumination, not other forms of self-reflection. Cognitive inflexibility, a characteristic feature of rumination (Davis & Nolen-Hoeksema, 2000), can also be observed in people low in openness (DeYoung, Peterson, & Higgins, 2005). With respect to the above findings, our data imply that in treatment-resistant depressed patients who are low in openness, cognitive inflexibility might be sustained by strong communication between sgACC and regions involved in cognitive control such as MCC. Relaxation of the connectivity strength

between sgACC and MCC could potentially promote the increases in openness and cognitive flexibility, which might also stimulate clinical improvements. Openness and depression indicators exhibit negative relationship (Khoo & Simms, 2018), and therapies for depression, such as Acceptance and Commitment Therapy and Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy, which focus on strengthening patients' openness, have been found effective in treating as well as preventing depression relapse (Hayes, Strosahl, & Wilson, 1999).

In the pre-session, a positive association was observed between openness and RSFC of cACC and pPCU seeds (*Figure 3* and *Table 2*). cACC demonstrated functional connections predominantly with dorsolateral and medial subregions of superior frontal gyrus (Li et al., 2013), areas implicated in supporting high-level functions of working memory (WM), particularly monitoring and manipulation of spatial and verbal information (Boisgueheneuc et al., 2006; DeYoung, Shamosh, Green, Braver, & Gray, 2009; Owen, 2000). The data show that treatment-resistant depressed patients who score high on openness also exhibit strong functional coupling between those brain areas that are supporting executive functions and WM. Several studies have demonstrated positive relationship between WM task performance and the levels of openness (for a review, see Waris, Soveri, Lukasik, Lehtonen, & Laine, 2018), suggesting that individuals expressing high openness might be more likely to employ brain systems involved in successful processing of information in WM tasks (DeYoung et al., 2009). In clinical depression, however, impaired performance in WM tasks has been observed, affecting both the executive processes, e.g. the ability to prioritise tasks, as well as the systems responsible for the temporary storage of auditory, visual and spatial information (Channon, Baker, & Robertson, 1993; Christopher & MacDonald, 2005). According to Christopher and MacDonald (2005), the impairments might be evoked by intrusive negative automatic thoughts, which can interfere with and disrupt cognitive processing. This suggestion is in line with the 'narrowing of attentional focus' theory, according to which the maintenance of depressogenic cognition seizes (demands a recruitment of) a fraction of attentional resources that would otherwise be available to engage and support the task performance (Ingram, 1984). In individuals with higher openness and arguably higher cognitive flexibility (Costa & McCrae, 1992), attentional resources might, therefore, be more likely allocated to subserve functionally beneficial cognition, as opposed to rigid, narrow and predominantly negative one often observed in depression (Beck, 1967). Be that as it may, our data seem to indicate that in treatment-resistant depressed patients, high levels of openness might ameliorate depression-

related cognitive impairments or facilitate cognitive processing, via recruitment of functionally connected brain regions involved in cognitive control and WM.

Despite the evidence supporting a positive relationship between the openness domain of personality and WM performance, the majority of studies inspecting the respective relationship yielded non-significant results, proposing facet-level investigations as more appropriate (Waris et al., 2018). As demonstrated by DeYoung and colleagues (2009), the openness domain consists of two equally important, related, yet separate sub-domains, namely openness to experience and intellect, which are associated with distinct aspects of cognition. The ideas facet of openness has been found a good indicator for the intellect sub-domain, while fantasy, aesthetics, feelings, and actions facets clearly marked the openness to experience sub-domain (DeYoung, Quilty, & Peterson, 2007). DeYoung and colleagues (2009) found that intellect, a construct reflecting ‘intellectual engagement and perceived intelligence’ (p. 884), was associated with WM task performance, and their relationship was mediated by neural activity within medial portion of superior frontal gyrus (area showing significant openness-related RSFC with cACC in the present study) and anterior prefrontal cortex. Conversely, openness to experience, which reflects ‘artistic and contemplative qualities related to engagement in sensation and perception’ (p 884), showed no such relationship. Facet-level investigations can prevent aggregation-related information loss and as such yield more meaningful insights for prediction of distinct behaviours (Paunonen & Ashton, 2001). Therefore, assessing sub-domain or facet-specific neural correlates of openness in healthy and depressed individuals, might inform how neural mechanisms associated with openness contribute to clinical improvements (condition).

In the pre-session data, a positive relationship was also observed between openness and RSFC of the pPCU seed (*Figure 3* and *Table 2*). The pPCU is thought to predominantly support processing of visual information, due to the connections it shares with extrastriate cortex, cuneus and dorsal lateral occipital region, as observed in macaque and humans (Colby, Gattass, Olson, & Gross, 1988; Margulies et al., 2009) The seed’s functional connections related to openness in the present study were, however, detected in areas comprising right primary motor cortex and frontal eye fields, as well as in subcortical thalamus. Thalamus is considered a ‘relay station’ transmitting information to the cerebral cortex. As such it is importantly involved in vision, e.g. receiving and propagating direct visual inputs from the retina to the striate cortex, as well as in motor control, e.g. receiving information from cerebellum, basal ganglia and superior colliculus, and transmitting it to motor cortex, supplementary motor area (SMA) and

frontal eye fields (FEF), respectfully (for a review, see Sommer, 2003). Right frontal eye field, also expressing significant relationship with openness in the present study, is particularly important for top-down control of visual selection (Hung, Driver, & Walsh, 2011) and attentional shifts (Buschman & Miller, 2009). The pattern of functional connections observed here, could, therefore, represent a distributed network subserving the integration of multimodal information and selection and execution of an appropriate action as a response to it. As demonstrated in the visually-instructed finger-movement task, primary motor cortex is involved in both, movement preparation and execution stages, while precuneus was active only in the execution stage, implying that its activity subserves attentive control of finger movement (Luo, Niki, Ding, & Luo, 2004). In depressed as opposed to healthy participants, impairments in psychomotor activity have been observed, affecting both the motor control, e.g. slower reaction time in visually-instructed task (Sévigny, Everett, & Grondin, 2003), as well as the cognitive component, e.g. the impaired allocation of attentional resources (Thomas, Goudemand, & Rousseaux, 1998). In the light of the findings presented above, our data seem to imply that in treatment-resistant depressed patients, higher levels of openness could promote higher levels of psychomotor activity via communication between brain regions supporting visual and motor control, as well as attention. A further speculation could imply that higher openness levels could be considered a protective factor for preservation of higher cognitive functions in depression. Interestingly, in a task assessing selective attention to emotional stimuli, Fiori and Antonakis (2012) demonstrated that faster correct responses could be predicted by higher levels of openness in healthy individuals. According to them, openness ‘might facilitate information processing when dealing with emotional stimuli’ (p. 242). The latter notion might be of special importance to depression, where information processing is subdued to negative bias (Beck, 1967).

However, an important consideration reflecting a general methodological limitation must be addressed at this point. fMRI signal can be detected as a result of excitatory *and/or* inhibitory activity, as they both increase metabolic demands (Logothetis, 2008). Unambiguously assigning a functional role to the observed (stimulus-related) active area can thus be problematic, as exemplified below. Walther and colleagues (2012) studied the relationship between resting-state cerebral blood flow (CBF; a marker of metabolic demand) and gross motor activity levels, objectively assessed by wrist actigraphy. In depressed patients, elevated morning CBF to supplementary motor area was a predictor of decreased gross motor activity during the rest of the day. This was seemingly counterintuitive, given that SMA activity implies

movement preparation, execution and motor control (Jenkins, Jahanshahi, Jueptner, Passingham, & Brooks, 2000). However, SMA activity is also involved in movement inhibition and halting the ongoing action (Chen, Scangos, & Stuphorn, 2010). Walther and colleagues (2012) argue, that the increased inhibitory neural activity and not excitatory is the one that expresses negative relationship with gross motor activity. With that in mind, the findings of the present thesis could, therefore, imply that openness exhibits a positive relationship with inhibitory- as opposed to excitatory- related functional connectivity between pPCU and motor-related areas. The finding implicating openness in fast reactive psychomotor responses denoted above (Fiori & Antonakis, 2012) most likely argues against it; however, a great deal of caution should nevertheless lead the interpretation.

4.2 Post-session data

A general increase in openness levels has been observed following psilocybin intervention relative to the pre-session scores. Openness levels at post-session have shown a positive relationship with RSFC of pgACC and pPCU seeds (*Figure 4 and Table 3*).

pgACC is crucially involved in social cognition, displaying activity during tasks that require participants to reflect on the mental states of the self or others, including own/other's thoughts and feelings (Amodio & Frith, 2006; Frith & Frith, 2003; S. C. Johnson et al., 2002). It is, therefore, held accountable for creating metacognitive representations, which are fundamental for high-level social interactions, as they allow us to build the self-knowledge, the knowledge about the others, as well as reflected self-knowledge, e.g. what other person knows/thinks about us (for a review, see Amodio & Frith, 2006). pgACC exhibited functional connections with an area spanning over the precentral and postcentral gyri, which are involved in sensorimotor integration (Pineda, 2008). These regions subserve the control of a person's own actions, but are in addition active when observing other people's actions (Rizzolatti & Sinigaglia, 2010). For instance, showing images of painful incidents happening to a third party was associated with increased activation in somatosensory areas in observers (Morrison, Tipper, Fenton-Adams, & Bach, 2013). According to Morrison and colleagues (2013), this activation could reflect the anticipation of sensory consequences of observed actions, suggesting that sensorimotor systems have an important role in social cognition, as they contribute to understanding of other people's actions and their consequences, which is an essential precondition for empathy. Similarly, facial expression recognition at least to some degree relies on the mimicry and underlying sensorimotor simulation associated with the mimicked

emotional state. The simulation of facial expression, therefore, at least partially evokes the respective emotional state in the imitator, which facilitates emotion recognition (Wood, Rychlowska, Korb, & Niedenthal, 2016). The latter finding is particularly important in the context of the present study for the following reasons. First, pgACC exhibited functional connections with lateral portion of sensorimotor area, which according to topography, represents a face region (Kalaska & Rizzolatti, 2013). Secondly, depressed patients exhibit impairments in the ability to recognise facial expressions, demonstrating poorer overall performance, slower response times, and a bias towards accurate processing of negative, particularly sad, stimuli (Csukly, Czobor, Szily, Takács, & Simon, 2009; Delle-Vigne, Wang, Kornreich, Verbanck, & Campanella, 2014). Thirdly, openness exhibits a positive relationship with facial emotional recognition task performance, suggesting that individuals who are more open are also more successful in recognising emotional states of others (Matsumoto et al., 2000; Antonio Terracciano, Merritt, Zonderman, & Evans, 2003). Finally, the administration of psilocybin or LSD has been shown to reduce the recognition of negative emotions and modulate amygdala responses associated with these stimuli (Bernasconi et al., 2014; Dolder, Schmid, Müller, Borgwardt, & Liechti, 2016; Roseman, Demetriou, Wall, Nutt, & Carhart-Harris, 2018; Schmidt, Kometer, Bachmann, Seifritz, & Vollenweider, 2013). In depression this effect correlated with the anti-depressive effects (Roseman et al., 2018). With respect to the previous findings, our data show that following a psilocybin intervention, depressed patients who are more open might also be more successful in processing the emotional states of other people via communication between pgACC and sensorimotor areas. This finding could suggest that psychedelic therapy decreases negative bias for facial expression recognition (and behaviour in general) through increasing the levels of openness, which might in turn allow a more successful mimicry and consequently, increased ability for emotion recognition.

In post-session data, a positive relationship was also observed between openness and RSFC of pPCU seed, which is, as already mentioned, involved in processing of visually-related information (Colby et al., 1988; Margulies et al., 2009). Its functional connections were confined to a cluster within bilateral frontal pole, whose activity has been implicated in exerting control related to external (stimulus-oriented) as well as internal (stimulus-independent) information (Burgess, Dumontheil, & Gilbert, 2007; Gilbert, Frith, & Burgess, 2005), while its anatomical projections have been shown to target visual cortex, among the others (Orr, Smolker, & Banich, 2015). Given that both pPCU and frontal pole share connections with visual areas, stronger functional coupling between pPCU and frontal pole, could imply enhanced

processing of visual information that either holds environmental or personal/self-generated salience. Based on monkey neurophysiological findings (Tsujimoto, Genovesio, & Wise, 2010), it has been proposed that the frontal pole neurons subserve retrospective monitoring of chosen goals (Tsujimoto, Genovesio, & Wise, 2011), or that they implement task-set-specific forward prediction models, which learn the action outcomes and contribute to deciding when switching to another task set is required (Koechlin, 2011). Either way, these suggestions hold relevance for depression, in which retrospective assessment of actions contributes to negative rumination and misinterpretations (American Psychiatric Association., 2013), and task-switching is impaired (Meiran, Diamond, Toder, & Nemets, 2011). Openness to experience and/or cognitive flexibility, on the other hand, are associated with decreased rumination (Davis & Nolen-Hoeksema, 2000) and increased ability to adapt to task-switching (Lepine, Colquitt, & Erez, 2000; Liu, Fan, Rossi, Yao, & Chen, 2016). Additionally, the work at The Centre for Psychedelic Research, Imperial College London (data not published), has recently found increases in cognitive flexibility following psilocybin administration in healthy participants. Our data show that following psilocybin administration, depressed patients who are high in openness also exhibit stronger communication between pPCU and frontal poles, a mechanism which might allow them to be more successful in flexibly controlling visual-modality specific external and internal impulses. The employment of this mechanism might in addition govern clinical improvements; given that openness exhibits a positive relationship with the neural substrates that support flexible retrospective/prospective cognition, increasing the levels of openness using a promising psilocybin intervention could potentially contribute to the reduction of clinical symptoms by enhancing cognitive flexibility via strengthening pPCU-frontal pole communication.

Given that the outcome of psilocybin interventions permits sample separation to responders and non-responders, the next step was to visually examine openness-RSFC within the two subgroups (*Figure 5*). RSFC of pgACC exhibited strong positive relationship with openness in both subgroups ($r = .91$ in responders and $r = .71$ in non-responders) and their correlations did not significantly differ; $p = .342$. Similarly, RSFC of pPCU displayed strong positive relationship with openness in both subgroups ($r = .70$ in responders and $r = .88$ in non-responders) and their correlations did not differ either; $p = .447$. Addressing our second hypothesis, the relationship between openness-RSFC observed within the whole sample does not seem to be driven by any subgroup-specific relationship, suggesting that neural mechanisms underlying clinical improvement can not be inferred, or that post-session clinical improvements

in responders might not depend on positive association between openness and pgACC/pPCU functional connectivity. However, the difference in the timing of the assessments could potentially contribute to indistinctive openness-RSFC relationships in the two subgroups. Namely, individuals classified as responders at one-week post-session might not display similar symptom reduction at three-months follow-up, when post-session openness inventory was applied. This could result in inappropriate separation of participants to two subgroups at three-months post intervention, and consequently openness-RSFC relationship at that time might not reflect how clinical improvements are mediated. Note again that this examination was exploratory in nature and the speculations proposed would require further empirical support, preferably with higher sample size.

4.3 General discussion, limitations, advantages

The patterns of functional connectivity related to openness before (*Figure 3* and *Table 2*) and after (*Figure 4* and *Table 3*) psilocybin intervention markedly differ. Several factors could account for the observed effects. First, psilocybin has been shown to promote increases in openness (as well as changes in extraversion and neuroticism; Erritzøe et al., 2018), which might concurrently result in functional reorganization within neural substrates supporting a given personality factor, rather than in simple intensification or weakening of the functional connections associated with that factor prior to psilocybin administration. As demonstrated by Lebedev and colleagues (2016), the acute LSD induces increases in brain entropy, that is shifts towards random dynamics, and these changes were predictive of openness increases two weeks later. This could imply that the extend of psychedelic-induced neural perturbation provides a window of opportunity mediating the extend of future personality changes. Secondly, previously homogenous sample of treatment-resistant depressed patients, at post-session consisted of individuals that responded to the treatment and the ones that did not. Psilocybin-induced clinical improvements (and increases in openness) in responders might reflect the relaxation of pathologically over-weighted priors or beliefs (negative bias), that are on a neural level encoded by spontaneous activity within high-level cortices (Carhart-Harris & Friston, 2019). This suggest that different patterns of spontaneous neural activity could be observed between responders and non-responders, providing the basis for markedly different openness-related RSFC before and after the treatment. Thirdly, at the time of the post-session fMRI scan, that is 24 hours after the psychedelic session, patients were arguably in a state of the so called ‘afterglow’ (Carhart-Harris et al., 2017; Maji, Schmidt, & Gallinat, 2015), which has been described as a state of elevated mood combined with a relative freedom from past concerns,

guilt and anxiety (Pahnke, 1969). Findings from neuroimaging show that under acute psychedelic experience, DMN undergoes modular disintegration, followed by a network re-integration post-acutely (Carhart-Harris et al., 2017). It is, therefore, possible that at the time of scanning, the network re-integration was still in process, which might have contributed to the observed differences between pre- and post- session openness-related RSFC patterns. Fourthly, the pre-session assessments, e.g. personality inventory NEO PI-R and fMRI scanning, have been timed shortly one after another, diminishing the possibility of any conspicuous events happening during the time between the two visits. On the other hand, the post-session assessment comprised an fMRI scan 24 hours after the psilocybin intervention, and a NEO PI-R personality assessment three months after the psilocybin treatment. This methodological drawback could potentially contribute to observing substantially different pre- and post- session RSFC patterns, as the neural correlates of post-session openness have been assessed before the traits have been allowed the real-life opportunities to manifest changes.

The present study was heavily based on the findings of Adelstein and colleagues (2011) in healthy volunteers, which show that openness can predict functional connectivity using *a priori* selected seeds within anterior cingulate and precuneus (*Figure 1* and *Figure 2*). Addressing our first hypothesis, the results of the present study in treatment-resistant depressed patients, collapsed across the seeds and the valence of the relationship they exhibit with openness, to some extent replicated the findings of Adelstein and colleagues (2011). Specifically, at pre-session (*Figure 3* and *Table 2*) the overlap with Adelstein's findings encompassed superior frontal gyrus, frontal pole, anterior cingulate gyri, and precentral gyrus, while middle frontal gyrus and subcallosal cortex exhibited contralateral preference across the two studies; in addition, the present study found functional connections within paracingulate gyrus and thalamus. At post-session (*Figure 4* and *Table 3*), the overlap with Adelstein's findings encompassed frontal pole, precentral and postcentral gyri; superior frontal gyri were found contralaterally; central opercular was specific to this study. Adelstein and colleagues detected a considerably more widespread activation pattern, that spanned, in addition to the regions already mentioned, across temporal and occipital cortices, as well as cuneus and precuneus. Nevertheless, the notable overlap across the findings of the two independent studies seems to suggest that those regions are crucially involved in supporting openness traits.

On the other hand, if taking into account each individual seed's RSFC pattern, the findings across the two studies markedly differ on several levels: the number and identity of the seeds expressing RSFC associated with openness, functional connections of those seeds, and the

valence of the openness-RSFC relationship. The factors that could have contributed to the observed differences are discussed below. First, the sample. Depression is characterised by neurobiological alterations, both on molecular level, e.g. a disruption of 5-HT, norepinephrine, and dopaminergic neurotransmitter systems (Maletic et al., 2007), as well as on functional level, e.g. abnormalities in dynamic connectivity among mPFC and PPC, regions that represent the core nodes of DMN (Berman et al., 2011; Lemogne et al., 2012). Given that the seeds' locations essentially overlap with the two nodes, the depressed patients' functional connectivity inferred from those seeds could, therefore, differ considerably from that of their healthy peers, potentially giving rise to the observed differences. Second, the sample size. The smaller sample size in this study (15) compared to the one of Adelstein and colleagues (39), might lack statistical power to replicate previous findings (Turner, Paul, Miller, & Barbey, 2018). Third, the analysis procedure. Even though the analysis pipeline of this study closely resembled the one of Adelstein and colleagues (2011), the use of different software packages for performing specific (pre)processing steps across the two studies, could have contributed its part to decreasing the degree of reproducibility, an issue that is receiving increasing attention within the field of fMRI research (Bowring, Maumet, & Nichols, 2018; Glatard et al., 2015).

Alternatively, dissimilarity between the findings of this study and of Adelstein and colleagues (2011) could imply that the selected seeds might not be adequate targets or that the seed-based RSFC in general might not be the optimal approach for investigating neural correlates of personality. An important methodological disadvantage of *a priori* seed selection is narrowing down the scope of obtainable information to those regions' functional connectivity. This creates the possibility of obtaining an incomplete pattern of neural correlates associated with personality factors by potentially omitting the seeds which are substantially contributing to embedding personality characteristics. Overcoming the constraints of hypothesis-driven seed-based approach and providing a more comprehensive insight into the neural correlates of personality might be achieved by employing large-scale data-driven methods (Kunisato et al., 2011) or predictive analyses using individual functional connectivity matrices (Dubois et al., 2018). To our knowledge, future studies are yet to utilise these methods for investigating neural correlates of personality beyond healthy participant populations.

Several limitations to this study, such as small sample size, *a priori* seed selection, deriving the hypothesis primarily from a single study in healthy participants (Adelstein et al., 2011), and ill-timing of post-session assessment, have already been addressed. Additionally, the lack of control group and a correlational nature of the relationship between openness and RSFC

constrains the interpretation of the findings. The conclusion of identifying cortical representations of inter-individual variation in openness can, therefore, as of yet not be delivered.

The present study, however, was the first to our knowledge that investigated neural correlates of openness in clinical depression as well as before and after potentially successful alternative psilocybin treatment intervention. As such, the findings can substantially contribute to understanding of how personality factors and clinical depression might be inter-related and sustained on neural level. Resting state functional connectivity analysis allows for the mapping of functional communication between brain regions, a mechanism which arguably underlies complex constructs, such as personality.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The scope of the present study was to examine for the first time neural correlates of openness in treatment-resistant depressed patients preceding and following a psilocybin-assisted treatment intervention. Openness to experience represents one of the Big Five personality factors and has been widely neglected in depression literature, which had its eyes fixed on investigating the relationship with neuroticism and extraversion, two personality factors with a long-standing and deep-seated involvement in psychopathology (Khoo & Simms, 2018). Openness is, however, getting assigned an important role in restoring of mental health, as accumulating evidence shows that it displays a negative association with depression indicators even after controlling for neuroticism and extraversion (Khoo & Simms, 2018), and that low openness can even be considered a risk factor for treatment-resistant depression (Takahashi et al., 2013).

The aim of the present study to identify neural correlates of openness in treatment-resistant depressed patients was an attempt of bridging the gap between personality neuroscience and underpinnings of depression-related neural dynamics. The findings of the present study preceding psilocybin intervention show an association between openness and RSFC among the brain regions that have previously been implicated in cognitive flexibility (Berman et al., 2011; Greicius et al., 2007), working memory (Boisgueheneuc et al., 2006; DeYoung, Shamosh, Green, Braver, & Gray, 2009; Owen, 2000), action selection and execution, as well as attentive control (Buschman & Miller, 2009; Hung et al., 2011; Luo et al., 2004). The data obtained after psilocybin intervention show that openness is related to RSFC between the areas supporting social cognition, such as understanding of other people's actions (Morrison et al., 2013) and recognition of emotional states (Wood et al., 2016), as well as task-switching and flexible retrospective/prospective cognition (Koechlin, 2011; Tsujimoto et al., 2011). Depression-related behavioural impairments on task performance assessing the cognitive abilities denoted above are well documented (Channon, Baker, & Robertson, 1993; Christopher & MacDonald, 2005; Csukly, Czobor, Szily, Takács, & Simon, 2009; Delle-Vigne, Wang, Kornreich, Verbanck, & Campanella, 2014; Meiran, Diamond, Toder, & Nemets, 2011; Sévigny, Everett, & Grondin, 2003), which stresses the importance of unravelling neural mechanisms that sustain them. Because openness and depression seem to be acting in opposite directions (e.g. facilitating and impairing information processing), increasing an individual's openness might signify clinically relevant outcomes, as certain therapies show.

Psilocybin intervention has been shown to hold promise for the treatment of depression (Carhart-harris et al., 2018) and was in addition found to promote the increases in openness (Erritzøe et al., 2018). As such, it might represent unique intervention for delivering insights on the interdependency between openness and depressive symptomatology, both on behavioural and neural levels. Future large-scale, randomised-controlled trials should be conducted to support the findings of the present study, which has been limited by its statistical power. Their focus in elucidating the openness-related neural mechanisms associated with psilocybin treatment response in depressed patients, should target the investigation of responders' and non-responders' specific patterns of functional connectivity using *separate* analyses for the two subgroups, which has not been done in the present study. Such analyses could unravel how openness-related functional connectivity might modulate clinical improvements.

6 REFERENCES

- Adelstein, J. S., Shehzad, Z., Mennes, M., Deyoung, C. G., Zuo, X., Margulies, D. S., ... Michael, P. (2011). Personality Is Reflected in the Brain ' s Intrinsic Functional Architecture, *6*(11). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0027633>
- American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders : DSM-5*. Arlington, VA : American Psychiatric Association.
- Amodio, D. M., & Frith, C. D. (2006). Meeting of minds: The medial frontal cortex and social cognition. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, *7*(4), 268–277. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn1884>
- Andrews-Hanna, J. R., Reidler, J. S., Sepulcre, J., Poulin, R., & Buckner, R. L. (2010). Functional-Anatomic Fractionation of the Brain's Default Network. *Neuron*, *65*(4), 550–562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2010.02.005>
- Andrews-Hanna, J. R., Smallwood, J., & Spreng, R. N. (2014). The default network and self-generated thought: Component processes, dynamic control, and clinical relevance. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, *1316*(1), 29–52. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.12360>
- Avants, B. B., Tustison, N., & Song, G. (2009). Advanced normalization tools (ANTs). *Insight Journal*, *2*, 1–35.
- Back, M. D., Schmukle, S. C., & Egloff, B. (2009). Predicting actual behavior from the explicit and implicit self-concept of personality. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *97*(3), 533–548.
- Balconi, M. (2013). Dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, working memory and episodic memory processes: Insight through transcranial magnetic stimulation techniques. *Neuroscience Bulletin*, *29*(3), 381–389. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12264-013-1309-z>
- Beaty, R.E., Kaufman, S. B., Benedek, M., Jung, R. E., Kenett, Y. N., Jauk, E., ... Silvia, P. J. (2016). Personality and complex brain networks: The role of openness to experience in default network efficiency. *Human Brain Mapping*, *37*(2), 773–779. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.23065>
- Beaty, R.E., & Silvia, P. J. (2013). Metaphorically speaking: Cognitive abilities and the production of figurative language. *Memory & Cognition*, *41*, 255–267.
- Beck, A. T. (1967). *Depression: Clinical, experimental, and theoretical aspects*. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Beck, A. T., Ward, C. H., Mendelson, M., Mock, J., & Erbaugh, J. (1961). An inventory for measuring depression. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, *4*, 561–571.
- Beckmann, M., Johansen-Berg, H., & Rushworth, M. F. S. (2009). Connectivity-based parcellation of human cingulate cortex and its relation to functional specialization. *The Journal of Neuroscience : The Official Journal of the Society for Neuroscience*, *29*(4), 1175–1190. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.3328-08.2009>
- Berman, M. G., Peltier, S., Nee, D. E., Kross, E., Deldin, P. J., & Jonides, J. (2011). Depression, rumination and the default network. *Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience*, *6*(5), 548–555. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scan/nsq080>
- Bernasconi, F., Schmidt, A., Pokorny, T., Kometer, M., Seifritz, E., & Vollenweider, F. X.

- (2014). Spatiotemporal Brain Dynamics of Emotional Face Processing Modulations Induced by the Serotonin 1A/2A Receptor Agonist Psilocybin. *Cerebral Cortex*, 24(12), 3221–3231. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bht178>
- Bjørnebekk, A., Fjell, A. M., Walhovd, K. B., Grydeland, H., Torgersen, S., & Westlye, L. T. (2013). Neuronal correlates of the five factor model (FFM) of human personality: Multimodal imaging in a large healthy sample. *NeuroImage*, 65, 194–208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2012.10.009>
- Boisgueheneuc, F. d., Levy, R., Volle, E., Seassau, M., Duffau, H., Kinkingnehun, S., ... Dubois, B. (2006). Functions of the left superior frontal gyrus in humans: a lesion study. *Brain*, 129(12), 3315–3328. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awl244>
- Bowring, A., Maumet, C., & Nichols, T. E. (2018). Exploring the Impact of Analysis Software on Task fMRI Results. *BioRxiv*, 285585. <https://doi.org/10.1101/285585>
- Bujang, M. A., & Baharum, N. (2016). Sample Size Guideline for Correlation Analysis. *World Journal of Social Science Research*, 3(1), 37. <https://doi.org/10.22158/wjssr.v3n1p37>
- Burgess, P. W., Dumontheil, I., & Gilbert, S. J. (2007). The gateway hypothesis of rostral prefrontal cortex (area 10) function. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 11(7), 290–298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2007.05.004>
- Busch, A. K., & Johnson, W. C. (1950). L.S.D. 25 As an aid in psychotherapy. *Diseases of the Nervous System*, 11(8), 241–243.
- Buschman, T. J., & Miller, E. K. (2009). Serial, Covert Shifts of Attention during Visual Search Are Reflected by the Frontal Eye Fields and Correlated with Population Oscillations. *Neuron*, 63(3), 386–396. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEURON.2009.06.020>
- Canli, T., Zhao, Z., Desmond, J. E., Kang, E., Gross, J., & Gabrieli, J. D. (2001). An fMRI study of personality influences on brain reactivity to emotional stimuli. *Behavioral Neuroscience*, 115(1), 33–42.
- Carhart-harris, R. L., Bolstridge, M., Rucker, J., Day, C. M. J., Erritzoe, D., Kaelen, M., ... Nutt, D. J. (2018). Psilocybin with psychological support for treatment-resistant depression : an open-label feasibility study. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 3(7), 619–627. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(16\)30065-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(16)30065-7)
- Carhart-Harris, R. L., Erritzoe, D., Williams, T., Stone, J. M., Reed, L. J., Colasanti, A., ... Nutt, D. J. (2012). Neural correlates of the psychedelic state as determined by fMRI studies with psilocybin. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(6), 2138–2143. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1119598109>
- Carhart-Harris, R. L., & Friston, K. J. (2019). REBUS and the Anarchic Brain: Toward a Unified Model of the Brain Action of Psychedelics. *Pharmacological Reviews*, 71(3), 316–344. <https://doi.org/10.1124/pr.118.017160>
- Carhart-Harris, R.L., Bolstridge, M., Rucker, J., Day, C. M. J., Erritzoe, D., Kaelen, M., ... Nutt, D. J. (2016). Psilocybin with psychological support for treatment-resistant depression: an open-label feasibility study. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 3(7), 619–627. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(16\)30065-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(16)30065-7)
- Carhart-Harris, R.L., Kaelen, M., Bolstridge, M., Williams, T. M., Williams, L. T.,

- Underwood, R., ... Nutt, D. J. (2016). The paradoxical psychological effects of lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD). *Psychological Medicine*, 46(7), 1379–1390.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291715002901>
- Carhart-Harris, R.L., Leech, R., Hellyer, P. J., Shanahan, M., Feilding, A., Tagliazucchi, E., ... Nutt, D. (2014). The entropic brain: a theory of conscious states informed by neuroimaging research with psychedelic drugs, 8, 1–22.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2014.00020>
- Carhart-Harris, Robin L., Roseman, L., Bolstridge, M., Demetriou, L., Pannekoek, J. N., Wall, M. B., ... Nutt, D. J. (2017). Psilocybin for treatment-resistant depression: FMRI-measured brain mechanisms. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1), 1–11.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-13282-7>
- Channon, S., Baker, J., & Robertson, M. M. (1993). Working memory in clinical depression: An experimental study. *Psychological Medicine*, 23, 87–91.
- Chen, X., Scangos, K. W., & Stuphorn, V. (2010). Supplementary motor area exerts proactive and reactive control of arm movements. *The Journal of Neuroscience : The Official Journal of the Society for Neuroscience*, 30(44), 14657–14675.
<https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2669-10.2010>
- Christopher, G., & MacDonald, J. (2005). The impact of clinical depression on working memory. *Cognitive Neuropsychiatry*, 10(5), 379–399.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13546800444000128>
- Clark, L. A., & Watson, D. (2008). Temperament: An organizing paradigm for trait psychology. In O. P. John, R. W. Robins, & L. A. Pervin (Eds.), *Handbook of personality: Theory and research* (pp. 265–286). New York: Guilford Press.
- Cohen, S. (1970). *The Beyond Within. The LSD Story*. Atheneum, New York.
- Colby, C. L., Gattass, R., Olson, C. R., & Gross, C. G. (1988). Topographical organization of cortical afferents to extrastriate visual area PO in the macaque: A dual tracer study. *The Journal of Comparative Neurology*, 269(3), 392–413.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/cne.902690307>
- Cordes, D., Haughton, V. M., Arfanakis, K., Carew, J. D., Turski, P. A., Moritz, C. H., ... Meyerand, M. (2001). Frequencies contributing to functional connectivity in the cerebral cortex in “resting-state” data. *American Journal of Neuroradiology*, 22(7), 1326–1333.
- Costa, P. T., Bagby, R. M., Herbst, J. H., & McCrae, R. R. (2005). Personality self-reports are concurrently reliable and valid during acute depressive episodes. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 89, 45–55.
- Costa, P. T., Herbst, J. H., McCrae, R. R., & Siegel, I. C. (2000). Personality at midlife: stability, intrinsic maturation, and response to life events. *Assessment*, 7, 365–378.
- Costa, P. T., & McCrae, R. R. (1992). *NEO-PI-R professional manual*. Odessa, FL: Psychological Assessment Resources.
- Costa, P. T., & McCrae, R. R. (2008). NEO PI-R - NEO Psychological Inventory, Revised Sample Report.
- Coutinho, J. F., Sampaio, A., Ferreira, M., Soares, J. M., & Gonçalves, O. F. (2013). Brain

- correlates of pro-social personality traits: A voxel-based morphometry study. *Brain Imaging and Behavior*, 7(3), 293–299. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11682-013-9227-2>
- Cox, R. W. (1996). AFNI: software for analysis and visualization of functional magnetic resonance neuroimages. *Computers and Biomedical Research*, 29, 162–173.
- Csukly, G., Czobor, P., Szily, E., Takács, B., & Simon, L. (2009). Facial Expression Recognition in Depressed Subjects. *The Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease*, 197(2), 98–103. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NMD.0b013e3181923f82>
- Dale, A. M., Fischl, B., & Sereno, M. I. (1999). Segmentation and surface reconstruction. *NeuroImage*, 9, 179–194.
- Davis, R. N., & Nolen-Hoeksema, S. (2000). Cognitive Inflexibility Among Ruminators and Nonruminators. *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, 24(6), 699–711. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1005591412406>
- Delle-Vigne, D., Wang, W., Kornreich, C., Verbanck, P., & Campanella, S. (2014). Emotional facial expression processing in depression: Data from behavioral and event-related potential studies. *Neurophysiologie Clinique*, 44(2), 169–187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucli.2014.03.003>
- Desikan, R. S., Ségonne, F., Fischl, B., Quinn, B. T., Dickerson, B. C., Blacker, D., ... Killiany, R. J. (2006). An automated labeling system for subdividing the human cerebral cortex on MRI scans into gyral based regions of interest. *NeuroImage*, 31(3), 968–980. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEUROIMAGE.2006.01.021>
- DeYoung, C.G., Shamosh, N. A., Green, A. E., Braver, T. S., & Gray, J. R. (2009). Intellect as distinct from Openness: Differences revealed by fMRI of working memory. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 97(5), 883–892.
- DeYoung, Colin G., Hirsh, J. B., Shane, M. S., Papademetris, X., Rajeevan, N., & Gray, J. R. (2010). Testing predictions from personality neuroscience. Brain structure and the big five. *Psychological Science : A Journal of the American Psychological Society / APS*, 21(6), 820–828. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797610370159>
- DeYoung, Colin G., Peterson, J. B., & Higgins, D. M. (2005). Sources of Openness/Intellect: Cognitive and neuropsychological correlates of the fifth factor of personality. *Journal of Personality*, 73(4), 825–858. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.2005.00330.x>
- DeYoung, Colin G., Quilty, L. C., & Peterson, J. B. (2007). Between Facets and Domains: 10 Aspects of the Big Five. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 93(5), 880–896. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.93.5.880>
- Dolder, P. C., Schmid, Y., Müller, F., Borgwardt, S., & Liechti, M. E. (2016). LSD Acutely Impairs Fear Recognition and Enhances Emotional Empathy and Sociality. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, 41(11), 2638–2646. <https://doi.org/10.1038/npp.2016.82>
- Dubois, J., Galdi, P., Han, Y., Paul, L. K., & Adolphs, R. (2018). Resting-State Functional Brain Connectivity Best Predicts the Personality Dimension of Openness to Experience. *Personality Neuroscience*, 1, e6. <https://doi.org/10.1017/pen.2018.8>
- Duman, R. S. (2004). Role of Neurotrophic Factors in the Etiology and Treatment of Mood Disorders. *NeuroMolecular Medicine*, 5(1), 011–026. <https://doi.org/10.1385/nmm:5:1:011>

- Ebmeier, K. P., Donaghey, C., & Steele, J. . (2006). Recent developments and current controversies in depression. *Lancet*, *367*(9505), 153–167.
- Erritzøe, D., Roseman, L., Nour, M. M., MacLean, K., Kaelen, M., Nutt, D. J., & Carhart-Harris, R. L. (2018). Effects of psilocybin therapy on personality structure. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, *138*(5), 368–378. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acps.12904>
- Etkin, A., Egner, T., & Kalisch, R. (2011). Emotional processing in anterior cingulate and medial prefrontal cortex. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *15*(2), 85–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TICS.2010.11.004>
- Fiori, M., & Antonakis, J. (2012). Selective attention to emotional stimuli: What IQ and openness do, and emotional intelligence does not. *Intelligence*, *40*(3), 245–254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.INTELL.2012.02.004>
- Forutan, F., Estalji, S., Beu, M., Nikolaus, K., Hamacher, K., Coenen, H. H., ... Larisch, R. (2002). Distribution of 5HT_{2A} receptors in the human brain: comparison of data in vivo and post mortem. *Nuklearmedizin- ...*, *41*, 197–201. Retrieved from <http://juser.fz-juelich.de/record/3434/files/10944.pdf>
- Frazier, J. A., Chiu, S., Breeze, J. L., Makris, N., Lange, N., Kennedy, D. N., ... Biederman, J. (2005). Structural Brain Magnetic Resonance Imaging of Limbic and Thalamic Volumes in Pediatric Bipolar Disorder. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, *162*(7), 1256–1265. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.162.7.1256>
- Frith, U., & Frith, C. D. (2003). Development and neurophysiology of mentalizing. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *358*(1431), 459–473. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2002.1218>
- Furr, R. M. (2009). Personality psychology as a truly behavioural science. *European Journal of Personality*, *23*(5), 369–401.
- Gilbert, S. J., Frith, C. D., & Burgess, P. W. (2005). Involvement of rostral prefrontal cortex in selection between stimulus-oriented and stimulus-independent thought. *European Journal of Neuroscience*, *21*(5), 1423–1431. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-9568.2005.03981.x>
- Glatard, T., Lewis, L. B., Ferreira da Silva, R., Adalat, R., Beck, N., Lepage, C., ... Evans, A. C. (2015). Reproducibility of neuroimaging analyses across operating systems. *Frontiers in Neuroinformatics*, *9*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fninf.2015.00012>
- Good, C. D., Johnsrude, I. S., Ashburner, J., Henson, R. N. A., Friston, K. J., & Frackowiak, R. S. J. (2001). A voxel-based morphometric study of ageing in 465 normal adult human brains. *NeuroImage*, *14*(1 D), 21–36. <https://doi.org/10.1006/nimg.2001.0786>
- Grabenhorst, F., & Rolls, E. T. (2011). Value, pleasure and choice in the ventral prefrontal cortex. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *15*(2), 56–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2010.12.004>
- Graziano, W. G., Habashi, M. M., Sheese, B. E., & Tobin, R. M. (2007). Agreeableness, empathy, and helping: A person x situation perspective. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *93*, 583–599.
- Greenberg, P. E., Fournier, A. A., Sisitsky, T., Pike, C. T., & Kessler, R. C. (2015). The economic burden of adults with major depressive disorder in the United States (2005 and

- 2010). *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 76(2), 155–162.
- Greicius, M. D., Flores, B. H., Menon, V., Glover, G. H., Solvason, H. B., Kenna, H., ... Schatzberg, A. F. (2007). Resting-State Functional Connectivity in Major Depression: Abnormally Increased Contributions from Subgenual Cingulate Cortex and Thalamus. *Biological Psychiatry*, 62(5), 429–437. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2006.09.020>
- Greicius, M. D., Krasnow, B., Reiss, A. L., & Menon, V. (2003). Functional connectivity in the resting brain: a network analysis of the default mode hypothesis. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 100(1), 253–258. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0135058100>
- Griffiths, R. R., Hurwitz, E. S., Davis, A. K., Johnson, M. W., & Jesse, R. (2019). Survey of subjective “God encounter experiences”: Comparisons among naturally occurring experiences and those occasioned by the classic psychedelics psilocybin, LSD, ayahuasca, or DMT. *PLoS ONE*, 14(4), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0214377>
- Griffiths, R. R., Johnson, M. W., & Carducci, M. A. (2016). Psilocybin produced substantial and sustained decreases in depression and anxiety in patients with life-threatening cancer. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, 30, 1181–1197.
- Griffiths, R. R., Johnson, M. W., Richards, W. A., B.D., R., McCann, U., & Jesse, R. (2011). Psilocybin occasioned mystical-type experiences: immediate and persisting dose-related effects. *Psychopharmacology*, 218, 649–665.
- Griffiths, R. R., Richards, W. A., Johnson, M. W., McCann, U. D., & Jesse, R. (2008). Mystical-type experiences occasioned by psilocybin mediate the attribution of personal meaning and spiritual significance months later. *Psychopharmacology*, 22(6), 621–632. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0269881108094300.Mystical-type>
- Griffiths, R. R., Richards, W. A., McCann, U., & Jesse, R. (2006). Psilocybin can occasion mystical experiences having substantial and sustained personal meaning and spiritual significance. *Psychopharmacology*, 187, 268–283.
- Grob, C. S., Danforth, A. L., Chopra, G. S., Hagerty, M., McKay, C. R., Halberstadt, A. L., & Greer, G. R. (2011). Pilot Study of Psilocybin Treatment for Anxiety in Patients With Advanced-Stage Cancer. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 68(1), 71. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archgenpsychiatry.2010.116>
- Hamilton, M. (1967). Development of a rating scale for primary depressive illness. *British Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, 6, 278–296.
- Hasler, F., Bourquin, D., Brenneisen, R., Bär, T., & Vollenweider, F. X. (1997). Determination of psilocin and 4-hydroxyindole-3-acetic acid in plasma by HPLC-ECD and pharmacokinetic profiles of oral and intravenous psilocybin in man. *Pharmaceutica Acta Helveticae*, 72(3), 175–184. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-6865\(97\)00014-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-6865(97)00014-9)
- Hofmann, A. (1968). Psychotomimetic agents. In A. Burger (Ed.), *Chemical constitution and pharmacodynamic actions*. M. Dekker, New York.
- Hofmann, A. (1980). *LSD: My problem child*. McGraw-Hill: New York.
- Howard, M. A., Volkov, I. O., Mirsky, R., Garrel, P. C., Noh, M. D., Granner, M., ... Brugge, J. F. (2000). Auditory cortex on the human posterior superior temporal gyrus. *The*

Journal of Comparative Neurology, 416(1), 79–92.

- Hung, J., Driver, J., & Walsh, V. (2011). Visual Selection and the Human Frontal Eye Fields: Effects of Frontal Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation on Partial Report Analyzed by Bundesen's Theory of Visual Attention. *The Journal of Neuroscience*, 31(44), 15904–15913.
- Hutton, C., Draganski, B., Ashburner, J., & Weiskopf, N. (2009). A comparison between voxel-based cortical thickness and voxel-based morphometry in normal aging. *NeuroImage*, 48(2), 371–380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2009.06.043>
- Ingram, R. E. (1984). Toward an information-processing analysis of depression. *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, 8(5), 443–477. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01173284>
- Jenkins, I. H., Jahanshahi, M., Jueptner, M., Passingham, R. E., & Brooks, D. J. (2000). Self-initiated versus externally triggered movements: II. The effect of movement predictability on regional cerebral blood flow. *Brain*, 123(6), 1216–1228. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/123.6.1216>
- Johnson, M.W., Garcia-Romeu, A., Cosimano, M. P., & Griffiths, R. R. (2014). Pilot study of the 5-HT_{2A}R agonist psilocybin in the treatment of tobacco addiction. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, 28, 983–992.
- Johnson, M.W., Sewell, R. A., & Griffiths, R. R. (2012). Psilocybin dose-dependently causes delayed, transient headaches in healthy volunteers. *Drug and Alcohol Dependency*, 123, 132–140.
- Johnson, M W. (2008). Human hallucinogen research : guidelines for safety.
- Johnson, Matthew W., & Griffiths, R. R. (2017). Potential Therapeutic Effects of Psilocybin. *Neurotherapeutics*, 14(3), 734–740. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13311-017-0542-y>
- Johnson, S. C., Baxter, L. C., Wilder, L. S., Pipe, J. G., Heiserman, J. E., & Prigatano, G. P. (2002). Neural correlates of self-reflection. *Brain*, 125(8), 1808–1814. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awf181>
- Jung, R. E., Segall, J. M., Bockholt, H. J., Flores, R. A., Smith, S. M., Chavez, R. S., & Haier, R. J. (2010). Neuroanatomy of creativity. *Human Brain Mapping*, 31(3), 398–409. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.20874>
- Kalaska, J. F., & Rizzolatti, G. (2013). Voluntary Movement: The Primary Motor Cortex. In E. R. Kandel, J. H. Schwartz, T. M. Jessell, S. A. Siegelbaum, & A. J. Hudspeth (Eds.), *Principles of Neural Science, Fifth Edition* (pp. 835–864). The McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc.
- Kelly, A. M. C., Di Martino, A., Uddin, L. Q., Shehzad, Z., Gee, D. G., Reiss, P. T., ... Milham, M. P. (2009). Development of anterior cingulate functional connectivity from late childhood to early adulthood. *Cerebral Cortex*, 19(3), 640–657. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhn117>
- Kennis, M., Rademaker, A. R., & Geuze, E. (2013). Neural correlates of personality: An integrative review. *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews*, 37(1), 73–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2012.10.012>
- Khoo, S., & Simms, L. J. (2018). Links between depression and openness and its facets. *Personality and Mental Health*, 12(3), 203–215. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pmh.1417>

- Koechlin, E., Danek, A., Burnod, Y., & Grafman, J. (2002). Medial Prefrontal and Subcortical Mechanisms Underlying the Acquisition of Motor and Cognitive Action Sequences in Humans. *Neuron*, *35*(2), 371–381. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0896-6273\(02\)00742-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0896-6273(02)00742-0)
- Koechlin, Etienne. (2011). Frontal pole function: What is specifically human? *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *15*(6), 241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2011.04.005>
- Kometer, M., Schmidt, A., Bachmann, R., Studerus, E., Seifritz, E., & Vollenweider, F. X. (2012). Psilocybin Biases Facial Recognition , Goal-Directed Behavior , and Mood State Toward Positive Relative to Negative Emotions Through different Serotonergic Subreceptors. *Biological Psychiatry*, *72*(11), 898–906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2012.04.005>
- Kraehenmann, R., Pokorny, D., Vollenweider, L., Preller, K. H., Pokorny, T., Seifritz, E., & Vollenweider, F. X. (2017). Dreamlike effects of LSD on waking imagery in humans depend on serotonin 2A receptor activation. *Psychopharmacology*, *234*(13), 2031–2046. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-017-4610-0>
- Kraehenmann, R., Preller, K. H., Scheidegger, M., Pokorny, T., Bosch, O. G., Seifritz, E., & Vollenweider, F. X. (2015). Psilocybin-induced decrease in amygdala reactivity correlates with enhanced positive mood in healthy volunteers. *Biological Psychiatry*, *78*(8), 572–581. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2014.04.010>
- Kraehenmann, R., Schmidt, A., Friston, K., Preller, K. H., Seifritz, E., & Vollenweider, F. X. (2016). The mixed serotonin receptor agonist psilocybin reduces threat-induced modulation of amygdala connectivity. *NeuroImage: Clinical*, *11*, 53–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nicl.2015.08.009>
- Krebs, T. S., & Johansen, P. (2012). Lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD) for alcoholism: meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, *26*, 994–1002.
- Kunisato, Y., Okamoto, Y., Okada, G., Aoyama, S., Nishiyama, Y., Onoda, K., & Yamawaki, S. (2011). Personality traits and the amplitude of spontaneous low-frequency oscillations during resting state. *Neuroscience Letters*, *492*(2), 109–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEULET.2011.01.067>
- Lebedev, A. V., Kaelin, M., Lövdén, M., Nilsson, J., Feilding, A., Nutt, D. J., & Carhart-Harris, R. L. (2016). LSD-induced entropic brain activity predicts subsequent personality change. *Human Brain Mapping*, *37*(9), 3203–3213. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.23234>
- Lemogne, C., Delaveau, P., Freton, M., Guionnet, S., & Fossati, P. (2012). Medial prefrontal cortex and the self in major depression. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, *136*(1–2), e1–e11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2010.11.034>
- Lepine, J. A., Colquitt, J. A., & Erez, A. (2000). Adaptability to changing task contexts: Effects of general cognitive ability, conscientiousness, and openness to experience. *Personnel Psychology*, *53*(3), 563–593. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.2000.tb00214.x>
- Li, W., Qin, W., Liu, H., Fan, L., Wang, J., Jiang, T., & Yu, C. (2013). Subregions of the human superior frontal gyrus and their connections. *NeuroImage*, *78*, 46–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2013.04.011>
- Li, X., Frye, M. A., & Shelton, R. C. (2012). Review of Pharmacological Treatment in Mood Disorders and Future Directions for Drug Development. *Neuropsychopharmacology*,

- 37(1), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1038/npp.2011.198>
- Liu, H., Fan, N., Rossi, S., Yao, P., & Chen, B. (2016). The effect of cognitive flexibility on task switching and language switching. *International Journal of Bilingualism*, 20(5), 563–579. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1367006915572400>
- Logothetis, N. K. (2008). What we can do and what we cannot do with fMRI. *Nature*, 453(7197), 869–878. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature06976>
- Lowe, M. J., Dzemidzic, M., Lurito, J. T., Mathews, V. P., & Phillips, M. D. (2000). Correlations in low-frequency BOLD fluctuations reflect cortico-cortical connections. *NeuroImage*, 12(5), 582–587. <https://doi.org/10.1006/nimg.2000.0654>
- Luo, J., Niki, K., Ding, Z. G., & Luo, Y. J. (2004). Precuneus contributes to attentive control of finger movement. *Acta Pharmacologica Sinica*, 25(5), 637–643.
- MacLean, K. A., Johnson, M. W., & Griffiths, R. R. (2011). Mystical experiences occasioned by the hallucinogen psilocybin lead to increases in the personality domain of openness. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, 25(11), 1453–1461. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0269881111420188>
- Madsen, M. K., Fisher, P. M., Burmester, D., Dyssegaard, A., Stenbæk, D. S., Kristiansen, S., ... Knudsen, G. M. (2019). Psychedelic effects of psilocybin correlate with serotonin 2A receptor occupancy and plasma psilocin levels. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, (September 2018), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41386-019-0324-9>
- Maji, T., Schmidt, T. T., & Gallinat, J. (2015). Peak experiences and the afterglow phenomenon : When and how do therapeutic effects of hallucinogens depend on psychedelic experiences ? <https://doi.org/10.1177/0269881114568040>
- Maletic, V., Robinson, M., Oakes, T., Iyengar, S., Ball, S. G., & Russell, J. (2007). Neurobiology of depression: an integrated view of key findings. *International Journal of Clinical Practice*, 61(12), 2030–2040. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1742-1241.2007.01602.x>
- Margulies, D. S., Vincent, J. L., Kelly, C., Lohmann, G., Uddin, L. Q., Biswal, B. B., ... Petrides, M. (2009). Precuneus shares intrinsic functional architecture in humans and monkeys. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 106(47), 20069–20074. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0905314106>
- Matsumoto, D., LeRoux, J., Wilson-Cohn, C., Raroque, J., Kookan, K., Ekman, P., ... Goh, A. (2000). A New Test to Measure Emotion Recognition Ability: Matsumoto and Ekman's Japanese and Caucasian Brief Affect Recognition Test (JACBART). *Journal of Nonverbal Behavior*, 24(3), 179–209. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1006668120583>
- Meiran, N., Diamond, G. M., Toder, D., & Nemets, B. (2011). Cognitive rigidity in unipolar depression and obsessive compulsive disorder: Examination of task switching, Stroop, working memory updating and post-conflict adaptation. *Psychiatry Research*, 185(1–2), 149–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PSYCHRES.2010.04.044>
- Moreno, F. A., Weigand, C. B., Taitano, E. K., & Delgado, P. L. (2006). Safety, tolerability, and efficacy of psilocybin in 9 patients with obsessive-compulsive disorder. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 67, 1735–1740.
- Moreno, J. L., Holloway, T., Albizu, L., Sealfon, S. C., & González-Maeso, J. (2011). Metabotropic glutamate mGlu2 receptor is necessary for the pharmacological and

- behavioral effects induced by hallucinogenic 5-HT_{2A} receptor agonists. *Neuroscience Letters*, 493(3), 76–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2011.01.046>
- Morrison, I., Tipper, S. P., Fenton-Adams, W. L., & Bach, P. (2013). “Feeling” others’ painful actions: The sensorimotor integration of pain and action information. *Human Brain Mapping*, 34(8), 1982–1998. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.22040>
- Mroczek, D. K., & Spiro, A. I. (2003). Modeling intraindividual change in personality traits: Findings from the normative aging study. *J Gerontol B Psychol Sci Soc Sc*, 58, 153–165.
- Nau, F., Yu, B., Martin, D., & Nichols, C. D. (2013). Serotonin 5-HT_{2A} Receptor Activation Blocks TNF- α Mediated Inflammation In Vivo. *PLoS ONE*, 8(10), 2–9. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0075426>
- Nichols, D. E. (2004). Hallucinogens. *Pharmacology & Therapeutics*, 101, 131–181.
- Nichols, D. E., Johnson, M. W., & Nichols, C. D. (2017). Psychedelics as Medicines: An Emerging New Paradigm. *Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, 101(2), 209–219. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpt.557>
- Orr, J. M., Smolker, H. R., & Banich, M. T. (2015). Organization of the human frontal pole revealed by large-scale DTI-based connectivity: Implications for control of behavior. *PLoS ONE*, 10(5), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0124797>
- Osmond, H. (1957). A review of the clinical effects of psychotomimetic agents. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 66, 418–434.
- Owen, A. M. (2000). The role of the lateral frontal cortex in mnemonic processing: the contribution of functional neuroimaging. *Experimental Brain Research*, 133(1), 33–43. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002210000398>
- Ozer, D. J., & Benet-Martinez, V. (2006). personality and the prediction of consequential outcomes. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 57, 201–221.
- Pacher, P., & Kecskemeti, V. (2004). Trends in the development of new antidepressants. Is there a light at the end of the tunnel. *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, 11(7), 925–943.
- Pahnke, W. N. (1969). The Psychedelic Mystical Experience in the Human Encounter with Death, 62(1), 1–21.
- Palomero-Gallagher, N., Vogt, B. A., Schleicher, A., Mayberg, H. S., & Zilles, K. (2009). Receptor architecture of human cingulate cortex: Evaluation of the four-region neurobiological model. *Human Brain Mapping*, 30(8), 2336–2355. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.20667>
- Paunonen, S. V., & Ashton, M. C. (2001). Big Five Predictors of Academic Achievement. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 35(1), 78–90. <https://doi.org/10.1006/JRPE.2000.2309>
- Pineda, J. A. (2008). Sensorimotor cortex as a critical component of an “extended” mirror neuron system: Does it solve the development, correspondence, and control problems in mirroring? *Behavioral and Brain Functions*, 4(1), 47. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1744-9081-4-47>
- Preller, K. H., & Vollenweider, F. X. (2018). Phenomenology , Structure , and Dynamic of Psychedelic States, (December 2016), 221–256. <https://doi.org/10.1007/7854>

- Réus, G. Z., Fries, G. R., Stertz, L., Badawy, M., Passos, I. C., Barichello, T., ... Quevedo, J. (2015). The role of inflammation and microglial activation in the pathophysiology of psychiatric disorders. *Neuroscience*, *300*(2015), 141–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroscience.2015.05.018>
- Rizzolatti, G., & Sinigaglia, C. (2010). The functional role of the parieto-frontal mirror circuit: interpretations and misinterpretations. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, *11*(4), 264–274. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn2805>
- Roberts, B. W., Luo, J., Briley, D. A., Chow, P. I., Su, R., & Hill, P. L. (2017). Psychological Bulletin A Systematic Review of Personality Trait Change Through Intervention A Systematic Review of Personality Trait Change Through Intervention. *Psychological Bulletin*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000088>
- Rohan, K. J. (2003). Mindfulness-based cognitive therapy for depression: a new approach to preventing relapse and overcoming resistance in cognitive therapy. *Psychiatry: Interpersonal & Biological Processes*, *66*, 272–281.
- Roseman, L., Demetriou, L., Wall, M. B., Nutt, D. J., & Carhart-Harris, R. L. (2018). Increased amygdala responses to emotional faces after psilocybin for treatment-resistant depression. *Neuropharmacology*, *142*, 263–269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropharm.2017.12.041>
- Ross, S., Bossis, A., Guss, J., Agin-Liebes, G., Malone, T., Cohen, B., ... Schmidt, B. L. (2016). Rapid and sustained symptom reduction following psilocybin treatment for anxiety and depression in patients with life-threatening cancer: a randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, *30*(12), 1165–1180. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0269881116675512>
- Rush, A. J., Trivedi, M. H., Wisniewski, S. R., Nierenberg, A. A., Stewart, J. W., Warden, D., ... Fava, M. (2006). Acute and Longer-Term Outcomes in Depressed Outpatients Requiring One or Several Treatment Steps: A STAR*D Report. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, *163*(11), 1905–1917. <https://doi.org/10.1176/ajp.2006.163.11.1905>
- Sackeim, H. A. (2001). The definition and meaning of treatment-resistant depression. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, *62*(SUPPL. 16), 10-17+35.
- Schmid, Y., & Liechti, M. E. (2018). Long-lasting subjective effects of LSD in normal subjects. *Psychopharmacology*, *235*(2), 535–545. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-017-4733-3>
- Schmidt, A., Komater, M., Bachmann, R., Seifritz, E., & Vollenweider, F. (2013). The NMDA antagonist ketamine and the 5-HT agonist psilocybin produce dissociable effects on structural encoding of emotional face expressions. *Psychopharmacology*, *225*(1), 227–239. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-012-2811-0>
- Sévigny, M. C., Everett, J., & Grondin, S. (2003). Depression, attention, and time estimation. *Brain and Cognition*, *53*(2), 351–353. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0278-2626\(03\)00141-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0278-2626(03)00141-6)
- Shackman, A. J., Salomons, T. V., Slagter, H. A., Fox, A. S., Winter, J. J., & Davidson, R. J. (2011). The integration of negative affect, pain and cognitive control in the cingulate cortex. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, *12*(3), 154–167. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn2994>
- Slotnick, S. D. (2017). Cluster success: fMRI inferences for spatial extent have acceptable false-positive rates. *Cognitive Neuroscience*, *8*(3), 150–155.

- Smith, K. (2014). Mental health: a world of depression. *Nature*, *515*(7526), 180–181.
- Smith, S. M., Jenkinson, M., Woolrich, M. W., Beckmann, C. F., Behrens, T. E. J., Johansen-Berg, H., ... Matthews, P. M. (2004). Advances in functional and structural MR image analysis and implementation as FSL. *NeuroImage*, *23 Suppl 1*, S208-19.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2004.07.051>
- Sommer, M. A. (2003). The role of the thalamus in motor control. *Current Opinion in Neurobiology*, *13*(6), 663–670. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conb.2003.10.014>
- Souery, D., Amsterdam, J., de Montigny, C., Lecrubier, Y., Montgomery, S., Lipp, O., ... Mendlewicz, J. (1999). Treatment resistant depression: methodological overview and operational criteria. *European Neuropsychopharmacology*, *9*, 83–91.
- Studerus, E., Gamma, A., & Vollenweider, F. X. (2010). Psychometric evaluation of the altered states of consciousness rating scale (OAV). *PLoS ONE*, *5*(8).
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0012412>
- Takahashi, M., Shirayama, Y., Muneoka, K., Suzuki, M., Sato, K., & Hashimoto, K. (2013). Low Openness on the Revised NEO Personality Inventory as a Risk Factor for Treatment-Resistant Depression. *PLoS ONE*, *8*(9), 1–7.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0071964>
- Terracciano, A., McCrae, R. R., Brant, L. J., & Costa, P. T. j. (2005). Hierarchical linear modeling analyses of the NEO-PI-R scales in the Baltimore Longitudinal Study of Aging. *Psychology and Aging*, *20*, 493–506.
- Terracciano, Antonio, Merritt, M., Zonderman, A. B., & Evans, M. K. (2003). Personality traits and sex differences in emotion recognition among African Americans and Caucasians. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, *1000*, 309–312.
<https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1280.032>
- Thomas, P., Goudemand, M., & Rousseaux, M. (1998). Divided attention in major depression. *Psychiatry Research*, *81*(3), 309–322. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-1781\(98\)00123-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-1781(98)00123-1)
- Tsujimoto, S., Genovesio, A., & Wise, S. P. (2010). Evaluating self-generated decisions in frontal pole cortex of monkeys. *Nature Neuroscience*, *13*(1), 120–126.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.2453>
- Tsujimoto, S., Genovesio, A., & Wise, S. P. (2011). Frontal pole cortex: encoding ends at the end of the endbrain. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *15*(4), 169–176.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2011.02.001>
- Turner, B. O., Paul, E. J., Miller, M. B., & Barbey, A. K. (2018). Small sample sizes reduce the replicability of task-based fMRI studies. *Communications Biology*, *1*(1), 62.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-018-0073-z>
- van den Heuvel, M. P., & Hulshoff Pol, H. E. (2010). Exploring the brain network: A review on resting-state fMRI functional connectivity. *European Neuropsychopharmacology*, *20*(8), 519–534. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.euroneuro.2010.03.008>
- Vollenweider, F. X., & Kometer, M. (2010). The neurobiology of psychedelic drugs: Implications for the treatment of mood disorders. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, *11*(9), 642–651. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn2884>

- Vollenweider, F. X., Vollenweider-Scherpenhuyzen, M. F. I., Bäbler, A., Vogel, H., & Hell, D. (1998). Psilocybin induces psychosis in humans via a serotonin-2 agonist action, *9*(17), 3897–3902.
- Walther, S., Höfle, O., Federspiel, A., Horn, H., Hügli, S., Wiest, R., ... Müller, T. J. (2012). Neural correlates of disbalanced motor control in major depression. *Journal of Affective Disorders, 136*(1–2), 124–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2011.08.020>
- Waris, O., Soveri, A., Lukasik, K. M., Lehtonen, M., & Laine, M. (2018). Working memory and the Big Five. *Personality and Individual Differences, 130*(March), 26–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2018.03.027>
- Wood, A., Rychlowska, M., Korb, S., & Niedenthal, P. (2016). Fashioning the Face: Sensorimotor Simulation Contributes to Facial Expression Recognition. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences, 20*(3), 227–240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2015.12.010>
- Xu, J., & Potenza, M. N. (2012). White matter integrity and five-factor personality measures in healthy adults. *NeuroImage, 59*(1), 800–807. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2011.07.040>
- Yarkoni, T. (2015). Neurobiological substrates of personality: A critical overview. In M. Mikulincer, P. R. Shaver, M. L. Cooper, & R. J. Larsen (Eds.), *APA handbook of personality and social psychology, Volume 4: Personality processes and individual differences* (pp. 61–83). Washington, DC, US: American Psychological Association.